

The business model of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator

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Authors:	Dimitra Tzani (IEECP), Vassilis Stavrakas (IEECP), Filippos Anagnostopoulos (IEECP)
Contributors:	Benedetto Grillone (CIMNE), Sotiris Papadelis (HEBES), Sidsel Bruun (SIN)

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Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
Factor4	Geert Goorden, Johan Coolen
RAP	Marion Santini

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AMV	Advanced Measurement & Verification
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BRP	Balance Responsible Party
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EnC	Energy Community

Acronym	Description
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEA	Energy Efficiency Aggregator
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measures
EEOS	Energy Efficiency Obligation Schemes
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M&V	Measurement and Verification
MUSH	Municipalities-Universities-Schools-Hospital
NYSERDA	New York State Energy Research and Development Authority
OP	Obligated Party
P4P	Pay-for-performance
PG&E	Pacific Gas and Electric Company
PM	Portfolio Manager
PrC	Prosumer Community
PV	Photovoltaics
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RFP	Request for Proposal
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TSO	Transmission System Operator
VPP	Virtual Power Plant

Executive summary

The Energy Efficiency Aggregator (henceforth EE Aggregator, or EEA) is a key energy market actor examined in the context of the SENSEI project. SENSEI focuses on the development of innovative pay-for-performance (P4P) schemes, where payments for energy efficiency are based on proven and measured savings. P4P (Pay-for-Performance) schemes are relatively new - especially their application in the residential sector, which have been tested in the US – and require solid and innovative business models to support their implementation.

The EE Aggregator and P4P programmes are being explored in the context of the Renovation Wave for meeting the EU's energy efficiency targets using innovative financing and new business models. Energy efficiency is one of the main pillars of energy and environmental policy to combat the adverse impacts of climate change. Although the implementation of energy efficiency interventions in the building sector is pivotal to drive the energy transition and achieve energy policy targets, energy efficiency investments and interventions remain critically low. Financial barriers (e.g., high upfront costs, high risk, uncertainty on return of investment, etc.) have been highlighted in the literature as the main factors hindering energy efficiency interventions.

The objective of this report is to analyse and explore the functions of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator. Early experience from the U.S.A. suggests that P4P programmes have been most successful when aimed at EE Aggregators rather than individual customers. An EE Aggregator is an aggregating entity that groups a sufficient number of buildings together into an energy savings portfolio. P4P schemes that make payments to aggregators appear better able to drive innovation in energy efficiency service delivery.

Aggregation in the energy sector

The aggregator model refers to a business approach, where an entity (the aggregator) operates between goods and service providers and consumers. The aggregator, in partnership with goods and service providers, offers their products among similar offers of other providers under its brand. Aggregators are part of our everyday life – a few examples include Airbnb, Uber, Netflix, Yelp, Amazon, and Spotify.

Aggregator business models are also implemented in the energy sector. Energy aggregators are legal entities that bundle and manage the consumption and/or generation

of distinct agents in a power system and their flexibilities to optimise electricity service market participation.

According to the European Commission¹, energy aggregation is defined as a “*function performed by a natural or legal person who combines multiple customer loads or generated electricity for sale, purchase or auction in any electricity market*”.

On the one side, aggregators develop energy services downstream for industrial, commercial or domestic customers who own generation and storage units or can offer demand response. On the other side, energy aggregators are offering value to the market players upstream such as Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs), Distribution System Operators (DSOs), Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and energy suppliers to optimize their portfolio and for balancing and congestion management.

Two aggregation approaches offering value to the power system are Demand Response (DR) and Virtual Power Plants (VPPs). DR facilitates voluntary and often automated changes by end-consumers of their usual electricity use patterns in response to market signals. It can assist in energy-load balance to reduce peak loads and electricity costs and improve the energy system’s reliability. VPPs offer a sizeable capacity, similar to that of a conventional generator, created by the aggregated operation of many distributed energy resources (generation and energy storage units) that can supply power without provoking grid congestion.

Both VPPs and DR aggregators are beneficial for system operators (TSOs and DSOs). DR aggregators support DSOs with network balancing services, such as the provision of reactive power, peak shifting and manual or automatic curtailment. VPPs assist the energy balancing market by employing available DER units, storage devices, and controllable loads. They contribute to the short term balancing (primary control) by the operation of virtual synchronous generators, such as rotating generators, supercapacitors, and fast batteries and in the medium term balancing (secondary control) by demand-side management.

¹ Article 2 (18) of Directive 2019/944

These types of aggregators have been set up because of the need for flexibility in power systems to accommodate the expansion of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), intermittent power generation by renewables, and new load peaks from the electrification of transport and heating. Small DERs are not able to participate individually in the power market because of market barriers, such as volume threshold for power producers. VPP aggregators bundle all these small DERs in one entity and trade their produced electricity in the power market. Without aggregation, this produced electricity could never reach end-users because of market entry barriers. Similarly for DR aggregators, due to their small electricity consumption and generation, individual residential and service sectors' consumers are not able to trade in electricity markets and contribute substantially to flexibility. Aggregators therefore overcome scale issues by grouping assets and trading their services in power markets on their behalf.

Flagship Pay-for-Performance programmes

The role of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator is new to the energy market and has progressed in the United States in the context of P4P-supported schemes. The resulting P4P programmes include support services that enable the aggregation of buildings into portfolios of energy savings, and thus allow to minimize the transaction costs of energy providers dealing with building owners. Two of the most well studied examples come from New York and California.

The New York State Energy Research and Development Authority (NYSERDA) and a utility partner (National Grid) choose one or more aggregators to implement EE services, either themselves and/or with subcontractors. The participating customers undergo EE upgrades as part of large portfolios of one- to four-family homes. Their energy savings are measured and aggregated on an ongoing basis over a period of three years after the interventions to calculate aggregators' compensation. Aggregators bid for the opportunity to join the program based on estimated savings, market intervention plan and bid price. The National Grid, as the utility administrator of the P4P Pilot, is responsible for screening and creating customer eligibility lists of households, managing performance and contractual relationships with EE Aggregators and distributing their performance payments.

Similarly, in California, PG&E administrates a residential P4P programme and selects several aggregators through a competitive procedure. Aggregators will engage with

residential homes to deliver EE retrofits. For a performance period of two years after the initial interventions, their energy savings are measured on an ongoing basis to calculate the aggregators' performance, according to which, PG&E rewards aggregators for the realised energy savings. This is practically a model where an integrated utility pays for delivered energy savings similar to how it procures supply-side resources.

Figure: The engagement of different actors in PG&E's residential programme.

The role of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator

Based on these and additional examples, mostly from North America, and knowledge collected from the literature, the SENSEI project has delivered a simplified understanding of the structure of Pay-for-Performance schemes and the role of the EE Aggregator. The following scheme indicates (on the left) the various sources of finance, and (on the right) the system for exploiting the energy efficiency potential of the building sector. The Energy Efficiency Aggregator has a central role bundling individual energy efficiency projects into portfolios, linking them to ESCOs, and securing financing through public and private entities aiming to invest in energy efficiency projects.

Figure: Interaction between the energy efficiency aggregator and the other market actors involved in the business model

Financial flows originate from public authorities subsidising EE programmes, TSOs & DSOs interested in using demand side resources for their grid benefits, and financial institutions that expect long-term returns on investment. Financing is channelled to ESCOs, which have the technical expertise for implementing energy efficiency measures in buildings. Savings are estimated using advanced M&V techniques. Periodic payments across this system are based on performance, and are collected from beneficiaries of EE measures (e.g. building owners, or TSOs & DSOs), and redistributed to ESCOs and Financial Institutions by the EE Aggregator.

An enabling energy market and legal framework needs to be set in place by a public authority, and a market facilitator is required to drive the development of the programme by analysing market conditions, proposing adaptations to the regulatory framework, and by setting enabling rules (e.g. for procurements) and the right infrastructure. The presented theoretical model constitutes a framework for conceptualising how to build a P4P programme, and the key roles of the EE Aggregator within it. The concrete specifications of each programme need to be decided in consultation with the involved stakeholders of the market in which the programme is to be carried out, and adjustments would need to be made to the regulatory environment.

The business model of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator

Based on the overall knowledge on Pay-for-Performance programmes and the role of the EE Aggregator, five business model archetypes have been developed representing adaptable approaches to participate in ambitious EE programmes:

- (1) Business archetype for offering flexibility in the energy system: Offering flexibility and balancing services to DSOs and TSOs.
- (2) Business archetype for energy service providers: ESCOs expanding their services and minimising performance risks.
- (3) Business archetypes for energy producers and energy companies: (3a) Utilities complying with energy efficiency obligations, and (3b) Utilities exploiting EE as a resource (e.g., an EE auction/ capacity market).
- (4) Business archetype for public authorities: Achieving large-scale energy savings, minimising public spending and leveraging private funding by engaging aggregators.
- (5) Business archetype for new roles: Energy communities using energy savings the same way they sell self-produced energy.

These single business archetypes can be combined into broader service offerings and business networks resulting in a unified EE Aggregator business model. The results of the analysis are summarised in the following Business Model Canvas template, while further explanation about the methodology is found in Section 6.2.

Key Partners	Key activities	Value Proposition	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
DSO(s), utilities, Electricity and gas distributors and retail sellers, ESCOs, investors, public authorities	Pool the building portfolio, Elaborate EEMs, Monitor the end-use consumption and calculate savings, aggregation	Limitation of the transaction costs of the EE upgrade, EE investment without the risks of underperforming upgrades, distribution of costs and responsibilities	Automated service, project-level (short-term) relationship with the building owners. Interacting and long-term relationship for the DSOs, utilities, electricity/ gas	DSOs, utilities, electricity/ gas distributors and retail sellers, MUSH, households, SMEs, public entities,

			distributors and retail sellers.	energy communities
	Key Resources		Channels	
	Financial/ energy experts and analysts, communication infrastructures, computational software, access to fundings, public incentives, regulatory framework		One stop shops, Calling center, Personal assistants, Social media, Website, Press, face-to-face meetings	
Cost Structures		Revenue Streams		
Dissemination campaigns, Experts' reward, Contractors' reward, Communication costs, Purchase of equipment and appliances, Transaction costs, procurement costs, public grid usage costs, capital costs for building and installing assets, technical and economic feasibility studies, planning costs		One-off funding from investors Regular payments per KWh or therms saved from building owners and utilities		

Summarizing, the EE Aggregator is the business entity that has the potential to play a leading role in the renovation market and accelerate the pace of EE retrofits in the building sector. It can engage hard-to-reach sectors, such as the residential, and create value for all engaged stakeholders. Due to the involvement of numerous market actors and the observed need for a regulatory drive, EU and national policymakers would need to support the establishment of P4P programmes and EE Aggregators by eliminating administrative barriers and providing a reliable and clear framework for all involved stakeholders to operate and interact.

1 Introduction

Energy use in buildings currently accounts for 36% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the European Union (EU) making buildings one of the largest contributors to EU emissions. In its long-term strategy for 2050, the European Commission (EC) recognises the need for a near-complete decarbonisation of the EU's building sector to meet its climate goals [1]. At the same time, European citizens have a lot to gain from the decarbonisation of buildings, including employment, health, lower household energy bills and system cost savings [2]. Despite the necessity, benefits and urgency of decarbonising buildings, it is one of the sectors that has arguably seen the least progress to date. The current annual renovation rate remains low in both residential and non-residential buildings and according to the EC, it must be at least double in the next ten years to achieve climate neutrality [3].

Renovation processes are lagging due to barriers at different points throughout the value chain – from the initial decision to engage in the renovation, to financing and completion of the project [4]. Major barriers are related to economic and information factors while other barriers are rather related to lack of interest or other priorities [5]. In particular, high investment costs and difficulty in accessing capital (e.g., especially in long-term borrowing) are often severe economic barriers affecting the renovation investment decision-making. High investment risk is another important hindering factor. Energy efficiency (EE) investments often pose a higher technical and financial risk, therefore requiring shorter payback periods and discouraging implementers and end-users [6]. A lack of understanding of the meaning and purpose of the EE actions and energy savings and the relationship between energy consumption and negative environmental impacts can lead to reluctance towards EE investments [7]. Finally, the lack of information on the technical parameters of various technologies and the renovation process leads to uncertainty regarding energy savings and retrofitting outcomes [8].

To kick-start a large-scale, sustainable deployment of renovation all over Europe, it is necessary to overcome the key barriers at every point of the supply chain [9]. However, public funds to finance EE investments and training programmes are frequently scarce and difficult to blend due to regulatory obstacles and lacking capacity in public administrations. Therefore, the involvement of private energy actors and financing sources are pivotal to implementing large scale retrofitting programmes [10].

The involvement of private sources of capital and energy market actors requires the existence of sustainable profit for the investors and all other actors involved, therefore it is necessary to establish suitable business models which can guarantee convenient conditions for all market players.

In this context, many studies have investigated which is the optimal business model to implement EE measures and renovation processes in the building sector. Qin et al. (2017) analysed different business models of the Energy Performance Contracting financing mechanism, which is one of the most popular market-based schemes promoting EE actions in the building sector. The study presents and explains four different EPC business models and proposes a multi-criteria decision-making method to facilitate the selection of an appropriate business model based on different criteria [11]. Tolkamp et. al. (2018) investigated what user-centred approaches to more sustainable business model design exist in practice and how they impact the market uptake of EE measures and present an analysis and refinement of the user-centred, sustainable business model concept [12]. Brown et. al. (2022) identified and analysed a typology of different energy service business models and discuss their potential for the key decarbonisation challenges in the residential sector [13]. Xue et. al. (2022) co-created a public–private–people partnerships business model to overcome the renovation barriers by improving information sharing, making use of operational experience and financial resources from the private sector, as well as political and financial support from the public sector [14]. Finally, Bianco et. al. (2022) employed the Value Flow Model to develop four business models to implement on-bill schemes, which are innovative financial frameworks for supporting investments in energy efficiency with a particular focus on residential buildings [15].

An emerging framework for supporting energy efficiency renovations is offered by Pay for Performance (P4P) schemes. There is a diverse spectrum of P4P programmes but, at the most basic level, these programs track and reward energy savings as they occur, usually by examining data from a building’s energy meters—as opposed to the more common approach of estimating savings in advance of installation and offering upfront rebates or incentives in a lump-sum payment. P4P programmes have existed in some form for 20 years, but primarily in the commercial and industrial sectors. With the increasing availability of household and business energy meter data and evolving data analysis techniques, there are new opportunities for deploying P4P programmes based on that data

[16]. Successful examples of these schemes can be found mostly in North America, but there have been some efforts also in Europe [3].

The P4P approach offers several key elements to address renovation challenges, often by involving power system actors such as utilities. With P4P, utilities can (1) align incentives with energy savings and grid value, (2) mobilize the ESCO market, and (3) deliver tailored solutions to their customers. P4P incentives may be directly tied to avoided costs for the energy system, thus encouraging the adoption and operation of resources that best align with utility needs. Utilities have access to capital for the initial investments required, and markets can be scaled up over time to address new needs, resources, and customer segments.

P4P incentives mobilize trade allies to deliver savings, and a non-prescriptive structure offers room for innovation, creating opportunities for whole-building solutions that deliver deeper, more cost-effective savings. Rather than tying themselves to one implementer, utilities can leverage the capabilities of many trade allies [15]. These trade allies are often referred to as Energy Efficiency Aggregators (EE Aggregators) in the existing energy efficiency P4P schemes. Implementing a P4P programme, thus, means that the administrative entity would enter into agreements with aggregators or building owners to purchase the energy efficiency levels monitored through the use of metered data. Compared to traditional energy efficiency programmes, the P4P programme allows for the performance risk of the project to be shifted from those who fund the programme (taxpayers or ratepayers) to the entities managing the project (e.g., energy service providers, aggregators, etc.). These entities often work with clients to choose which measures to install, are responsible for the quality of their installation, and provide advice on how to optimise their operation. Thus, by incentivizing ESCOs and contractors to pay more attention to performance, their incentives align with the programme goals and the risk of underperformance can be reduced.

Despite the multiple benefits of these schemes, as discussed by Tzani et. al. (2022) [16], the literature on P4P programmes is rather scarce and it is limited to the framework level, without analysing the details of possible business models which could be practically implemented by utilities or other interested entities. The present study aims at bridging this gap by providing a structured approach to the analysis of five business models by employing the Business Model Canvas. In this regard, the contribution of the present study includes:

- The introduction of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator (EEA) as a market actor and the presentation of different aspects of its role and its activities within the framework of a P4P programme;
- The identification of all stakeholders involved in the EEAs' business model and the mapping of the relationships between them;
- The definition of all aspects of the business model, such as the necessary collaborations, transactions, revenue streams, customer segments, resources and costs.

We address these questions by following the methodological steps presented in **Section 2**. First, we analyse the concept of aggregation and the role of aggregators in the energy sector in **Section 3**. Then the role of the EE Aggregator in two real-world case studies is presented in **Section 4** and relevant stakeholders are identified and analysed in **Section 5**. Based on previous literature and our data, we then develop a typology of EE Aggregator business models and explore emerging examples in **Section 6**. **Section 7** presents the insights from the online collaborative workshop we conducted and the online survey to better formulate the EE Aggregator business model. We conclude in **Section 8** after discussing the key findings of our study.

2 Methods

This section presents the methodological approach we used to reach the objectives and the overall goal of this study. The approach consists of four main methodological steps that are presented below.

Step 1: Literature Review

Initially, extensive desk research in the existing literature was performed to gather information about the concept of aggregation. The material we reviewed consisted of academic papers, grey literature, and real case studies. The key topics that we focused on were:

- Existing aggregator models in business
- Aggregators in the energy sector:
 - Aggregators' various types and business models
 - Aggregators' drivers, challenges and benefits to other energy market actors and the grid
- The concept of the EE Aggregator and P4P schemes
- The role of aggregators in existing P4P programmes

Key information identified during these steps supports the stakeholders and business model analysis of the next steps.

Step 2: Stakeholder analysis

In this step, we identify, define and analyse the role of stakeholders that are directly or indirectly involved in the EE Aggregator business model and the interactions between them.

Step 3: Business model development

In Step 3 we design and develop the business model of the EE Aggregator. The development of the business model helps understand which building topology, which investment scenario and which boundary conditions, can allow the EE Aggregator to build a positive business case. Initially, multiple business model archetypes are developed each one related to different EE Aggregator's responsibilities, involved parties, monetary flows and financial source(s). The Business model is formed according to these typologies and information extracted from previous steps, using the building blocks of the Business

Model Canvas (BMC) as a framework. The BMC method is the common approach in analysing business and service concepts, by describing the product, customer interface, infrastructure management and financial aspects of the model in nine different subtopics. **Table 1** presents the nine blocks of the BMC accompanied by a brief description and leading questions of the analysis that will identify the core elements of the canvas.

Table 1. Questions included in the Business Model Canvas.

BMC Component	Questions that underlie a BMC
Customer segment	<p><i>Who are we creating value for? Who are our most important consumers?</i></p> <p>This element defines the multiple groups of individuals or organizations an enterprise tries to attract and serve [17]. In order to improve customers satisfaction, a company may classify customers into specific segments with standardised requirements, essential characteristics, or different attributes [18].</p>
Value propositions	<p><i>What value do we deliver to the customer? What problem are we helping to solve? What needs are we helping to address? What set of products and services are we offering for each customer segment?</i></p> <p>This element identifies the products and services that incentivise each customer segment and describes them regarding their economic, environmental and social aspect [19]. It is what motivates customers to change from one company to another. It is a package of advantages that an organization offers to its customers, how it takes care of their issue or fulfils their requirements. [18]</p>
Channels	<p><i>Through which channels do our customer segments want to be contacted? How do we reach them now? How do our channels integrate? Which one works best? Which are the most cost-effective? How are they integrated into the customers' routine?</i></p> <p>This element determines how a company addresses its customers and manages to transfer value proposition. Channels are customer meeting points that raise their awareness of the company's products and services, help them evaluate the Value Proposition and purchase several products and services, communicate the Value Proposition to them and provide them with post-purchase customer support. [17–19]</p>
Customer relationships	<p><i>What type of relationship does each of our customer segments expect us to establish with them? Which ones have we already established? How do they integrate with the rest of our business model?</i></p>

	<p>This element represents the form of the necessary connections and relationships that a company establishes with each Customer Segments in order for the business model to work.</p>
Revenue streams	<p><i>What amounts are our customers willing to pay? What do they currently pay for? How would they prefer to pay? How much does each source of revenue contribute to the total revenue?</i></p> <p>This item specifies the money a company earns from each Customer Segment. These rewards can be either transaction income due to one-off customer payments or recurring income due to regular payments.</p>
Key resources	<p><i>What key resources does our value proposition require?</i></p> <p>This element defines the essential financial, human, intellectual and physical resources required to operate the business model and enable the company to create and deliver value, acquire markets, support relationships with customer segments and generate revenues [17–19].</p>
Key activities	<p><i>What key activities does our value proposition require?</i></p> <p>This element characterizes the most vital actions that a company must perform in order to effectively operate its business model, create and deliver a Value Proposition, acquire markets, support Customer Relationships, and generate credit [18,19].</p>
Key partners	<p><i>Who are our main partners? Who are our main suppliers? What key resources are we getting from what partners? What key activities do partners perform?</i></p> <p>This element describes the network of necessary alliances, such as producers and partners that the company uses in order to optimise its business models, reduce risks and uncertainty or acquire specific assets and activities [18].</p>
Cost structures	<p><i>What are the most important costs in our business model? Which key features are most expensive? Which key activities are most expensive?</i></p> <p>This element includes all the fixed and variable costs, such as creating and transferring value, maintaining relationships with customers and all other costs involved in making the profit that is required to operate the business model.</p>

Step 4: Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement activities have been implemented to better understand the stakeholders' needs and attitudes towards the developed EE Aggregator business model. In particular, the activities in Step 4 facilitate i) Understanding the barriers to implementing the EE Aggregator business models from the perspectives of the

stakeholders identified in Step 2; ii) Highlighting the benefits of the proposed business model iii) Identifying the main drivers for the implementation of the business model.

This process is based on a workshop with key stakeholders (**Section 6.3.1**) and two online EU-wide surveys (**Section 6.3.2**). Workshops are a good choice to assess the potential feasibility of the proposed model and are considered an efficient approach for future-oriented study. The workshop has its advantages from the following aspects. First, it can gather opinions, knowledge, and needs from the public sector, private sector, and residents, which provides a basic understanding. Second, during the process, participants in the workshop can expose potential problems earlier, which can help make strategies for alternative scenarios. Finally, different stakeholders can express their opinions in the process, helping them understand each other, and negotiate the detailed application of the business model. This can also enhance relations and communications, as well as promote the practice and acceptance of the decisions. Furthermore, as a second step and in order to enhance the findings of our study with feedback from a broader range of stakeholders we conducted an online survey.

Online collaborative workshop

An online workshop was organised on March 18th 2022 in collaboration with the Horizon 2020 projects frESCO and Ambience. The workshop², titled “*From commercial to residential: Extending energy performance contracts*”, focused on how EPCs can expand in the residential sector through innovative business models. In this context, SENSEI presented the function of the EE Aggregator business model within the P4P schemes focusing on the added value it can bring to the residential sector.

EU-wide online surveys

Before the workshop, a survey was developed in collaboration with the other two research projects to collect feedback from different stakeholders and discuss the results of the survey on the day of the workshop. This enhanced the participation of the stakeholders in the development process of the business model and allowed for a co-creation procedure increasing the possibilities of acceptance of the model, with emphasis placed on the residential sector. For more information see **Appendix A**.

² The recording is available at <https://youtu.be/BkkXVQ4KvM8>

A second survey was created to include aspects from all the archetypes of the business model (e.g., public sector, energy communities, etc.) and validate or further elaborate our findings regarding the business model overall. For more information see **Appendix C**.

3 Existing aggregator business models

The objective of **Section 3** is to introduce the concept of aggregation. **Section 3.1** presents the aggregation approach in business. In **Section 3.2**, the key features of aggregators in the energy sector are analysed and existing aggregation business models are investigated. **Section 3.3** describes the drivers for energy aggregators' existence, the benefits produced for the energy system and other energy agents and the challenges of aggregation in the energy sector.

3.1 Aggregator model in business

The aggregator model refers to a business approach, wherein an entity (the aggregator) operates between producers or service providers and consumers of the specific goods produced or services provided [20]. Both goods/ services providers and consumers are the aggregator's customers, and the aggregator provides services to both of them without, in most cases, possessing any manufacturing or warehousing capability [21,22]. **Figure 1** illustrates how the concept of aggregated services works.

Figure 1. How the aggregator business model works (Source: [23]).

The aggregator creates a domain that offers uniform quality and prices and allows consumers to conveniently select the prices and specifications of products and/or services provided according to their needs [20]. To do so, the aggregator signs a partnership

contract with the goods or services provider and sells them among similar offers of other providers under its brand [22,24]. Marketing activities are commonly within an aggregator's responsibility and charge [25]. Such activities often include pursuing to attract consumers and offering contract-defined revenues to the providers [20,25]. The concept of the aggregation approach may seem complicated, yet aggregator entities are part of our everyday life [20]. **Table 2** presents examples of aggregator entities used broadly in our daily life and a short description of their services.

Table 2. Common aggregators and the services they offer.

Aggregators	Types of services
Airbnb [26]	Accommodation search aggregation services, integrating property and customer management.
Uber [27]	Motor Vehicle aggregators, acting as digital mediators or marketplaces for passengers to connect with a driver for the intent of transportation.
Netflix [28]	Video streaming service aggregators are search aggregation services that scan multiple video streaming sites to list movies and TV shows available on various platforms.
Yelp, Rotten Tomatoes [29]	Review Aggregators are websites or software applications that typically gather and display user or expert reviews of a specific service or product from various online sources.
LinkedIn, Google Jobs [30]	Job Aggregators aggregate and display job postings from various career sites, employer job listings, and other job posting sites at a single platform.
Amazon [31]	Shopping Aggregators collate results of several shopping engines and offer price, product and rating comparisons.
Spotify [32]	Music aggregator enabling artists to distribute their music on a global scale through specifically digital services.

To get a better sense of how aggregators have traditionally operated:

- **Airbnb** does not build hotels or lease apartments. It is the site that travellers turn to when they are looking for a place to stay.
- **Uber** does not own cars or hire drivers. It is the first app that people open when they need to get somewhere.

- **Spotify** doesn't produce songs. It is a music aggregating service that offers access to millions of songs.

Because customers turn to aggregators first when they are looking for services, suppliers need to adapt to the rules and preferences of the aggregators. Airbnb hosts optimize their homes, listings and pricing based on what Airbnb's customers prefer. Uber drivers are friendly, and reliable and provide high-quality services hoping for 5-star ratings. Demand gives aggregators unprecedented power over commoditized suppliers. This enables aggregators to shift the chokepoint in the value chain from supply to demand.

3.2 Aggregators in the energy sector

Besides the above well-established aggregation examples, aggregator business models are also implemented in the energy sector. Energy aggregators are legal entities that bundle and manage the consumption and/or generation of distinct agents in a power system and their flexibilities to optimise electricity service market participation [33–36].

According to the Electricity Directive (2019/944), energy aggregation is defined as a “*function performed by a natural or legal person who combines multiple customer loads or generated electricity for sale, purchase or auction in any electricity market*” [37].

In other words, aggregators are facilitators between the two sides of electricity markets [38]. On the one hand, they develop energy services downstream for industrial, commercial or domestic customers who own generation and storage units or can offer demand response. On the other hand, energy aggregators are offering value to the market players upstream such as Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs), Distribution System Operators (DSOs), Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and energy suppliers to optimize their portfolio and for balancing and congestion management [36].

The precise definition of an aggregator can be restricted or expanded according to regulations that define its roles and activities [7]. **Different actors in the power system can become aggregators, causing aggregators to have different roles** [39]. Two aggregation approaches broadly discussed in practice that can provide flexibility potentials in the electricity system are **Demand Response (DR)** and **Virtual Power Plants (VPPs)**. For each of these aggregation models, there is a variety of roles. Below, DR and VPP models are presented followed by their many different existing roles, each one of them representing a different type of aggregator business model.

3.2.1 Demand Response Aggregator

According to the EC, DR is defined as “*voluntary changes by end-consumers of their usual electricity use patterns—in response to market signals*”[40]. In other words, DR is the shift of electricity consumption of consumers in response to external factors [39,41–43]. Such external factors could be electricity price signals and incentive, reward or penalty schemes used by DR programs in order to persuade consumers to shift their electricity demand [44]. Thus, through DR end-consumers are able to assist in energy-load balance in order to reduce peak loads and electricity costs and improve the energy system’s reliability [45–47]. Apart from providing the energy system with consumers’ flexibility, DR aggregators can create market power for the consumers by representing them as one entity to the actors in electricity markets and helping them earn money by offering financial rewards [43]. **Figure 2** represents the interaction between a DR aggregator and agents of the electricity system.

Figure 2. The engagement of DR aggregator with electricity market agents (Source:[45]).

According to the empirical findings of Stede et al. [39] from the German power sector, a DR aggregator often has the following roles to practice. First, they have to identify all the demand-side flexibility potentials of new customers and help them realise these potentials on their premises. Then, the aggregator has to activate flexibility potentials to the required degree and depth of automation. In order to sell customers’ flexibility in the electricity market, an aggregator has to provide customers with hedging solutions to stabilize revenues. Also, bundling several services across electricity and other energy markets may result in additional benefits, for example by combining the roles of energy retailer and

aggregator. DR aggregators function through different business models based on the responsibilities the aggregator has and the stakeholder relations between the energy actors [48].

3.2.2 Virtual Power Plant

VPPs is a “sizeable capacity” similar to that of a conventional generator created by the aggregated operation of many distributed energy resources (DERs) [35,43]. The aggregated DERs are able to offer renewable energy sources (RES) without provoking grid congestion [49,50]. This structure enables aggregators to sell electricity or ancillary services via an electricity exchange, in the wholesale market, or through procurement by the system operator [35]. At the core of all VPP models lies the Information Communication Technology (ICT) system that collects and processes information about weather forecasts, electricity prices in wholesale markets and the overall power supply and consumption trends [35]. This information is used to predict power generation from non-dispatchable RES energy and the future electricity demand, optimise the operation of all aggregated dispersed DERs and facilitate their coordination [51]. Apart from ICT, a VPP model also consists of generation units [52] and/or energy storage units [39,53]. Generation technology in VPPs includes both supply-side flexibility and DR flexibility [52]. Supply-side flexibility in DER portfolios involves Distributed Generation (DG) units [52], such as Combined Heat and Power (CHP), biomass and biogas, small power plants, solar and wind generation [39,53]. DR flexibility in DER portfolios refers to flexible loads and energy storage [52]. Flexible loads are loads or consumption patterns shifted in response to external signals (e.g., heating, cooling, and charging of electrical vehicles) [43,49]. The possession of energy storage units facilitates aggregators to shift electricity consumption and generation in time [39]. **Figure 3** illustrates the participation of VPP in the power system and the information and electricity transmission between all the engaged parts.

Figure 3. Mapping of VPP engaging with the rest power agents (Source: [35]).

There is a variety of different business models appearing across Europe for VPPs aggregators. These business models are classified according to the different services and specific functions of the aggregators, the responsibilities they uptake and the different stakeholder interactions between the actors involved [54].

3.3 Why were energy aggregators established?

Following the overview of the existing energy aggregators concepts, the present section presents the reasons that led to the development of the energy aggregators and explores the benefits they bring to the energy system overall and the actors involved in it.

The increasing integration of RES in the electricity market has driven the quest for flexibility in power systems. Increasing electrification of the transport sector, the expansion of DERs, intermittent RE generation, and new load peaks from EV charging and heat pumps, challenge all the involved agents of the energy sector. As a result, new technologies, management strategies and control and optimization algorithms are essential to guarantee the reliability of the energy system [55–57].

In this context, the concept of the aggregator has emerged to ensure market integration and flexibility of demand and generation and to decrease the reliance on RES support schemes [57].

3.3.1 Drivers of energy aggregation

Small DERs are not able to participate individually in the power market because of market barriers, such as volume threshold for power producers. VPP aggregators bundle all these small DERs in one entity and trade their produced electricity in the power market. Without aggregation, this produced electricity could never reach end-users because of these market barriers [44].

The same driver led to the DR aggregators' development. Due to their small electricity consumption and generation, individual residential and service sectors' consumers are not able to trade in electricity markets and contribute substantially to flexibility. Aggregators can overcome this issue by grouping consumers' assets and trading their flexibility in various electricity markets on their behalf [40].

Information and communication technologies are required to participate in market bidding and receive control signals, but put significant extra costs to small suppliers and DER agents. It is more economically efficient for a VPP aggregator to centralize computing power, allowing decentralized agents to use only inexpensive computing equipment that receives simple control signals [58].

Consumers often lack information [59] on when system peaks may occur, on the prices of various services, on available technologies that may help manage consumption, on the prices of these technologies, etc. A DR aggregator can gather and forecast all the aforementioned information, which is critical for hedging risk or scheduling bids and consumption, and translate it into quantity bids in a market [60].

Finally, hedging against price risks is an option mostly available for large agents with an adequate understanding of financial markets. A DR aggregator, acting as an intermediate between large and small agents, may be able to provide hedging solutions to small consumers/producers too [61].

3.3.2 Aggregation benefits for the energy system and the market players

VPP aggregators can reduce transaction costs for DER agents due to their centrality in the marketplace and their economies of scale in managing information [62]. A lot of often fixed transaction costs, such as registering within a system or acquiring required insurance against economic losses and reporting requirements among other things, are associated with participating in the electricity market. Additional costs are all the inherent costs of

acquiring and engaging a customer [63]. For a small supplier or DER agent, these costs are largely fixed and represent a high transaction cost per unit of the output sold [64]. Some of these costs may be unnecessary or inefficiently allocated; regardless, there will be fundamental value in increasing the number of services provided or procured per market agent and spreading fixed market and regulation costs across more agents [34].

Both VPPs and DR aggregators are beneficial for system operators (TSO and DSO). DR aggregators support DSO with network balancing services, such as the provision of reactive power, peak shifting and manual or automatic curtailment. Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs) are also benefited from both VPPs' and DR aggregators' operations. VPPs assist the energy balancing market by employing available DER units, storage devices, and controllable loads [35]. They can contribute to the short-term balancing (primary control) by the operation of virtual synchronous generators, such as rotating generators, supercapacitors, and fast batteries and in the medium-term balancing (secondary control) by demand-side management, i.e. increasing the generation of reserve DER units and decreasing the demand [65].

A DR aggregator controls and uses consumers' assets in order to provide all the beneficial services to all the electricity market agents and for that offers financial rewards to the consumers according to their assigned contracts [39]. In some cases, large power plants are producing electricity in order to satisfy just a small quantity of demand, leading to a higher cost of power production. Instead, a DR aggregator might be able to eliminate the load by shifting demand and therefore reduce the marginal cost [43]. Also, resources included in a VPP aggregator can replace the peak power plant by dispatching the aggregated distributed generation technologies and energy storage (e.g. batteries) [35].

An aggregator can group and manage the DERs to provide real-time operating reserve capacity that can participate in ancillary markets when needed. Using already connected energy resources, through aggregators, can minimise the investment needed in additional capacity [43]. By providing demand-side management and load shifting, an aggregator can minimize investments in transmission and distribution grid reinforcements [35,43].

Another benefit of DR aggregation is the democratization of the electricity market. DR aggregators offer the opportunity to end users and prosumers to trade flexibility and become an active part of the electricity market [66]. On their own, small DERs and prosumers, face market access barriers such as fees, administrative complexity and

exclusive rules that limit their profitability, and as such are not motivated to participate in the electricity market. But their engagement is crucial to secure the power system's stability and reliability. Engaging with a VPPs or DR aggregator can offer financial rewards to DERs and prosumers, but they also offer automation [7].

4 The concept of the energy efficiency aggregator

While the concept of DR aggregators and VPPs has been extensively explored in the literature, the concept of aggregators operating in EE projects has not. This section introduces the concept of the EE Aggregator and explores existing EE programmes working with EE Aggregators.

The role of the EE Aggregator has not yet been established and is new to the energy market. Therefore, its definition, capabilities and interfaces with other energy parties have not been explored in the literature. An EE Aggregator, similarly to DR aggregators and VPPs, can have different functions and roles including attracting customers, aggregating a sufficient number of buildings together into an energy savings portfolio, monitoring and evaluating the criteria for joining and selecting the projects, looking for investors and defining the EE programme. Based on the literature review of existing aggregators' models, the EE Aggregator can bring added value to EE programmes by lowering transaction costs and creating economies of scale. Furthermore, aggregation in EE programmes can facilitate the transition to a decentralized energy system with high shares of intermittent RES by using a dedicated demand-side aggregator of flexibility and EE capacities on the household level to support grid operators.

The establishment of EE Aggregators has progressed in the United States in the context of P4P-supported schemes. The resulting P4P programmes include support services that enable the aggregation of buildings into portfolios of energy savings. This aggregation in portfolios minimizes the transaction costs of energy providers dealing with building owners. P4P programmes that make payments to EE Aggregators appear to drive innovation in EE service delivery.

To further clarify the concept of EE Aggregation, its role and responsibilities in a P4P scheme and to identify the necessary stakeholders involved in such a scheme, two real P4P case studies that are in place in the U.S. are presented in the next sections.

4.1 “Home Energy Savings Program” Pay for Performance Pilot in New York

4.1.1 Overview

<p>Responsible entity</p>	<p>Home Energy Savings Program is a residential P4P programme administered by the New York State Energy Research and Development Authority (NYSERDA) and National Grid.</p> <p>NYSERDA is a New York State public-benefit corporation promoting EE and the use of RES.</p> <p>National Grid is a multinational utility providing electricity and gas to more than 20 million people throughout New York, Massachusetts, and Rhode Island.</p>
<p>Summary</p>	<p>NYSERDA and a utility partner choose one or more aggregators to implement EE services, either themselves and/or with subcontractors. The participating customers, that undergo EE upgrades, are part of large portfolios of one-to-four-family homes. Their energy savings are measured and aggregated on an ongoing basis, over a period of three years after the interventions to calculate aggregators’ compensation.</p>
<p>Purpose</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the use of EE as a grid resource. • Achieve large-scale energy savings and compensate accordingly. • Attract new EE investments. • Offer space for innovative business models and technologies to emerge.
<p>Start date and duration</p>	<p>The “Home Energy Savings Program” Pay for Performance (P4P) was launched in mid-2021. Selected Portfolio manager(s) (PMs), implementers and aggregators, will be awarded a five-year contract with National Gas, comprising of a two-year Implementation Period during which PMs can enrol customers and</p>

	implement interventions at customer sites, and three years for the completion of project performance periods during which payments will be made for metered energy savings.
Location	State of New York, United States
Coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Oneida County, Onondaga County and Oswego County ▪ 1,500 selected Electricity and Natural Gas customers in One-to-Four-Family Homes
Website	https://www.nyserda.ny.gov/All-Programs/Home-Energy-Savings-Program https://www.nationalgridus.com/News/2020/11/NYSERDA-and-National-Grid-Partner-to-Launch-Innovative-8216-Home-Energy-Savings-Program-8217-in-Central-New-York-/

4.1.2 P4P structure

Involved actors

The following actors are involved in the scheme:

- **NYSERDA** is the administrator of the P4P pilot [67]. NYSERDA is responsible for managing the Advanced Measurement & Verification (AMV) solution provider, fund performance payments that are distributed by National Grid, document P4P pilot processes and maintain Home Energy Savings website. Also, NYSERDA conducts pilot evaluation with support from evaluation contractor, implement measurement and verification (M&V) Plan and manage Non-Routine Events and Non-Routine Adjustments (NRAs), along with payment impacts, with National Grid's input and finally, supports customer awareness and marketing efforts [68].
- **National Grid** is the Utility Administrator of the P4P Pilot and is mainly responsible for screening and creating customer eligibility lists, managing performance and contractual relationship with PMs and distributing PMs' performance payments. It is, also, responsible for developing email campaigns, and social media marketing strategies for customer education and awareness,

maintaining National Grid pilot website with information on customer offerings and evaluate pilot scalability and portfolio performance [68,69].

- **Aggregators** are the PMs of the P4P Pilot. They bid for the opportunity to join the program based on estimated savings, market intervention plan, and bid price. Aggregators may select to partner with Contractor(s), for services such as project installations, marketing and/or customer acquisition [67,70]. The role of aggregator(s) and their main responsibilities in this pilot are presented in detail in the next section.
- **Recurve Analytics, Inc** is the AMV Solution Provider. It develops a baseline for each project and conducts all energy data and related savings analysis utilizing the CalTRACK methodology in its Demand Flexibility Platform [71].
- **Eligible Customers** are a pool of 200.000 One-to-Four-Family Homes in Oneida, Onondaga and Oswego Counties that are National Grid electricity and natural gas customers[67]. Among them, 1.500 will participate in the P4P program and will benefit from aggregators EE upgrades [69,71]. Eligible Customers must provide at least 14 consecutive months of available billing data and their household income must be greater than 80% of Area Median Income [68].

The interactions of the above-mentioned actors in the framework of Home Energy Savings Program are mapped in **Figure 4**. To simplify the concept of this figure, contractors are not included, but could be considered under portfolio managers and alongside EE services.

Figure 4. The engagement of different actors in Home Energy Savings Programme

Aggregators and their responsibilities

NYSEDA and the utility partner issue a request for proposal (RFP) to select one or more energy service providers (implementers and aggregators), referred to as PMs, to implement EE solutions either themselves and/or with subcontractors. The role of aggregators and their main responsibilities within the framework of the Home Energy Savings Program were described thoroughly in the RFP and are presented below [68]. First, aggregators bid in order to get the opportunity to join the program as PMs. Then, they sell EE upgrade services to eligible customers leveraging marketing provided by NYSEDA and National Grid and provide their monthly reports on market activities, including sales pipeline, customer outreach, and quality assurance and quality control inspections. Aggregators have to utilize the National Grid provisioned Customer Authorization Form for obtaining authorization from Customers for the access, transfer, and visibility of customers' utility consumption data to all authorized representatives of the Recurve, NYSEDA, and PM Company. Customers cannot be enrolled in the pilot without a completed Customer Authorization Form. In order to secure customer participation, EE aggregators identify and acquire financing, implement EEMs and manage operational cash flows. They also have to implement EE interventions and make efforts to ensure interventions meet or exceed energy savings targets submitted and approved during the bid process. EE Aggregators and Contractors need to comply with

National Grid's Information Security Policies and Standards and they must agree to provide National Grid Security vulnerability scan reports such as Code Scan Report, Penetration Test Report, Web Application Vulnerability Scan if requested. Additionally, they should perform quality assurance and quality control inspections (QA/QC) to ensure quality of work completed, verify that measures have been installed in accordance with building codes, local permit and licensing requirements and that it follows pilot protocols, ensure that proper building science techniques are followed for each measure installed, and proper health and safety techniques are followed, such as those established by the Building Performance Institute, or equivalent. Furthermore, aggregators should assist with user acceptance testing for the AMV Platform prior to the commencement of the Implementation Period, obtain payment recommendations generated by Recurve and submit them to National Grid for invoice review and approval and to collaborate with NYSERDA and National Grid relative to serving low and moderate-income (LMI) customers. A few more specificities have been set in place, where post-contract execution and before the program launch and performing services, aggregators must provide a written certification of compliance with, at minimum, the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1AA and Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), based on an independent third-party audit that scrutinizes and confirms PM's compliance with WCAG 2.1AA.

Performance assessment

Recurve handles real-time data on consumption provided by smart meters and performs all energy data and related savings analysis using the CalTRACK methodology in its Demand Flexibility Platform [71]. CalTRACK is a set of open-source, empirically validated and replicable methods for calculating energy savings by comparing weather normalized pre-and post-retrofit energy use for a given portfolio of customers. Aggregators have access to individual customers and aggregated portfolio data, providing analytics and insights into realised savings and opportunities [72].

Reward mechanism

Aggregators are responsible for submitting the approved Payment Recommendation generated by the AMV Solution Provider, and invoice along with the Purchase Order number to National Grid. Payment issuance is performed by National Grid contingent

upon NYSERDA’s approval of the Payment Recommendation from the AMV Platform [68].

Payments are done quarterly starting from the performance period initial date. After the intervention period, each project within the portfolio receives a total of one Initial Payment and three Annual Adjusted Payments. All payments are performance-based, and PMs/aggregators are not entitled to receive their entire contract value if savings are not delivered. The payment/energy unit (kWh or therm) rate is determined depending on the bids presented by aggregators [73]. It would therefore be different for each portfolio, but it should not be higher than the Levelised Cost ceiling of \$14/MMBtu (about 43 EUR / MWh) [68]. The methodology to assess the remuneration is presented in references [73] and [68] from NYSERDA.

4.2 Pacific Gas and Electric Company – Residential Pay-for-Performance Programmes in California

4.2.1 Overview

Responsible entity	The Pacific Gas and Electric Company (PG&E) is an American investor-owned utility (IOU) with publicly traded stock. The company is headquartered in the Pacific Gas & Electric Building, in San Francisco, California. PG&E provides natural gas and electricity to 5.2 million households in the northern two-thirds of California, from Bakersfield and northern Santa Barbara County, almost to the Oregon and Nevada state lines.
Summary	PG&E, which administrates the residential P4P programme, selects several aggregators through a competitive procedure. Aggregators will engage with residential homes to deliver EE upgrades. For a performance period of two years after the initial interventions, possible savings will be measured on an ongoing basis to calculate the aggregators’ performance, according to which, PG&E will reward aggregators for the realised energy savings.
Purpose	PG&E’s Residential Pay-for-Performance Program seeks to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish a model that pays for delivered EE savings similar to how it procures supply-side resources. 2. Accomplish significant energy savings and compensate accordingly, regardless of how businesses deliver these solutions. Allow aggregators to determine the most attractive mix of interventions.

	3. Establish a scalable model for the residential EE market by engaging aggregators.
Start date and duration	PG&E launched the residential P4P program in 2016 with an initial enrolment period of 2 years and annual incentive payments to Aggregator(s) for two years after the initial interventions are performed. PG&E proposes to continue to measure and claim the savings for at least another 1-3 years to better inform future program design and properly value measures with a longer useful life.
Location	California, United States of America
Coverage	4,200 Electricity and Natural Gas customers of PG&E in Residential Homes
Website	https://www.pge.com/en_US/residential/save-energy-money/resources/energy-efficiency-resources/third-party-energy-efficiency-programs.page

4.2.2 P4P Structure

Involved actors

The following actors are involved in the scheme:

- The **California Senate** sets EE goals (Senate Bill 350) [74].
- The **California Public Utilities Commission** (regulator) reviewed and approved the pilot programme [74].
- **PG&E**, an energy utility, is the administrator of the residential P4P pilot programme. PG&E is managing performance through the AMV Solution Provider, selects third-party aggregators through a competitive solicitation and funds their performance payments [74].
- **Aggregators** directly or through a network of **contractors** conduct EE interventions in customers' houses in order to maximize measurable savings [75]. The role of aggregator(s) and their main responsibilities are presented in the next section.
- **Recurve Analytics, Inc** is the AMV Solution Provider selected by PG&E. It develops a baseline for each project and conducts all energy data and related savings analysis utilizing the CalTRACK methodology [76].

- **Customers** are 4.200 residential houses that are PG&E electricity and natural gas customers. They must provide at least 12 consecutive months of available billing data before the initial intervention [74].

The way all these actors are cooperating is presented in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. The engagement of different actors in PG&E's residential programme.

Aggregators and their responsibilities

Aggregators are responsible for managing a portfolio consisting of numerous residential homes that receive EE interventions to maximize energy savings from those sites. They work directly with residential customers and contractors to achieve energy savings through retrofits in addition to operational and/or behavioural interventions. Aggregators may consist of existing market actors such as Property Accessed Clean Energy (PACE) loan providers, smart thermostat producers, vertically integrated contractors, program implementers or may be new entrants in the California market.

The role of aggregators and their main responsibilities within the framework of PG&E's P4P programme are described thoroughly in the RFP and are hereby presented in summary [74]. Initially, aggregators bid their \$/kWh and \$/therm savings into an auction in order to participate in the program. The selected aggregators conduct marketing and outreach to eligible potential customers and engage with contractors, if necessary. They determine the advertising, incentives and materials needed to recruit and educate customers.

Aggregators provide PG&E with existing customer data to help establish baselines for claimable savings. The mix of interventions that is most attractive to each customer, including behavioural, operational, and retrofit activities is defined by the aggregator, and along with contractors, they make sure that their work conforms to best practices. The business model of both aggregators and their contractors is to focus on equipment replacement versus repair due to the higher sale or loan price. This program builds upon this by financially motivating aggregators and contractors to identify early replacement opportunities for equipment, and to maximize the installation of heating ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) equipment and shell insulation measures. Aggregators report to PG&E intervention tactics and associated implementation dates to inform the evaluation process. Upon feedback from the CalTRACK portfolio tracking dashboard and/ or household level analytics that aggregators are conducting on their own, along with contractors they should adjust customer offerings, as needed to ensure energy savings are being realized. Finally, the aggregator is responsible for providing customers with insights into their energy usage patterns and striving to maximize the savings achieved. Customers with solar photovoltaics (PV) or who add solar PV while enrolled must provide verifiable production data to calculate energy savings to allow for paying incentives to aggregators for that site.

Performance assessment

The savings estimates are conducted through the CalTRACK system, a set of open source, empirically validated and replicable methods for comparing weather normalized pre-and post-retrofit energy use focused on transparency, standardization, and broad stakeholder input [72]. For each house, the program makes use of energy consumption data from 12 months before the initial implementation of EEMs. The savings estimated from each house are used to calculate the aggregator's portfolio performance, mitigating the risk that some homes will have neutral or negative savings. Participating customers cannot receive any other utility EE incentives. To calculate claimable net savings, PG&E can use several evaluation and M&V methods, including a quasi-experimental approach with nonequivalent comparison groups that matches "treatment" and "control" customers. This approach is in addition to self-reported surveys to estimate net-to-gross ratios [74].

Reward mechanism

PG&E proposes to pay a set \$1.8/therm and \$0.80/kWh rate to implementers for gross savings annually for two years starting from the performance period initial date [74]. The

program does not provide any up-front payments for savings [77]. An additional 5 to 10 per cent bonus incentive is offered to aggregators for net savings. Kickers eventually may be added to motivate higher savings, longer life measures, and bigger net savings [74].

5 Stakeholder analysis of the energy efficiency aggregator concept

This section analyses the main energy market actors involved in the EE Aggregator business model and their main roles and interactions. Stakeholder interaction is increasingly recognised as an essential component of sustainable business models, playing an important role in sustainable value propositions, creation and capture [78]. Therefore, the development of the business model and the definition of its different typologies require the understanding of influencing stakeholders and their needs, goals and roles in the energy business. A map of stakeholders that are directly or indirectly involved in the EE Aggregator business model is presented in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Possible stakeholders having influence on the energy efficiency aggregator's business model

Some of the stakeholders are more directly involved in delivering, receiving, financing or contributing to the EEMs than others. Based on the P4P examples explored in **Section 4** and the SENSEI stakeholder identification/engagement activities we conclude that, besides the EE Aggregator, stakeholders that are more directly involved in the business model, are *end-users (e.g., building owners or tenants), ESCOs, electricity suppliers, DSO/ TSOs, investors and financiers (such as banks etc.), smart technology and renovation equipment providers, public authorities, energy communities.*

Building on these key stakeholders we establish the business ecosystem for the EE Aggregator business model as illustrated in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7. The business ecosystem of the most relevant stakeholders.

5.1 Actor characterisation

The key market actors of the EE Aggregator model are analysed below. In particular, we describe each actor and explain its role within the scheme. We base our analysis on the already existing business models and we consider that the EE Aggregator business model is applied in the context of a P4P programme. This allows us to be more specific and descriptive on the role of each actor and its interactions.

Energy Efficiency Aggregator

Description:

The EE Aggregator bundles together EE services to facilitate the creation of innovative EE schemes and programmes. Its role might also include the role of DR aggregator creating in this way a demand-side flexibility aggregator role, which manages at the same time responsive (dispatchable) demand-side flexibility and more permanent flexibility linked to re-shaping the load curve of certain users through specific Energy Efficiency measures (EEMs).

Role:

The main role of the **EE Aggregator** in the context of performance-driven EE programmes is to facilitate the aggregation of individual EE projects into portfolios, set up the necessary M&V techniques and channel the available financing that will help ESCOs and contractors to implement EEMs. Financial inflows are channelled through the EE Aggregator, from investors, system operators, public authorities, and energy retailers to ESCOs, who have the technical expertise to implement energy renovation measures in the selected buildings and facilities. Ultimately, the EE Aggregator is the market player responsible for operationalizing the P4P programme. Its responsibilities include among others: the project acquisition and aggregation, the evaluation of projects according to predefined technical and financial eligibility criteria, the management of the interactions between different stakeholders, and finally the implementation of M&V calculations.

DSO and TSO**Description:**

DSOs are entities responsible for distributing electricity from the substations to the final points of consumption, i.e. buildings, industrial complexes etc. [79]. DSOs have to maintain the distribution facilities and guarantee the quality of supply, while also being in charge of metering the supply points [80]. Generally, the distribution networks are connected to the transmission grids, which transport electricity over larger distances and at higher voltages [80]. In addition, there are cases where DSOs are subject to legislative mechanisms, such as the Energy Efficiency Obligation Schemes (EEOS) provided for in Art. 7 of the EE Directive in the EU jurisdiction, and are required to fulfil EE targets that contemplate the execution of interventions of the end users' buildings [81].

TSOs are entities entrusted with transporting electricity on a national or regional level, using the fixed infrastructure [82]. Due to the high fixed costs of establishing a transmission infrastructure, such as power lines, substations, and control infrastructure, TSOs are usually a natural monopoly, and as such, they are often subjected to regulations [83]. Transmission grids transport large quantities of high (and extremely high) voltage electricity across vast distances [82], usually connecting large power plants to the outskirts of large cities or industrial zones,

where the voltage is lowered and the electricity is distributed to all end users through the distribution network.

TSOs in a wholesale energy market are also responsible for monitoring the power system's security in real-time and coordinating the supply and demand for electricity in a way that eliminates frequency variations or supply interruptions [84]. TSOs must provide a continuous (second-by-second) balance between energy supply from power plants and demand from consumers, as well as the availability of reserves to cover unexpected events [84].

Role:

DSOs and TSOs are typically responsible for maintaining the stability of the distribution and transmission grid. Thus their main interest in EE lies in avoiding grid congestion and maintaining grid reliability. Participating in a P4P EE scheme can provide system operators with new cost-efficient ways to guarantee grid reliability by investing in both dispatchable and long-term demand-side flexibility solutions while enabling them to align with EEO schemes and achieve end-use efficiency targets. The financial inflow coming from system operators would then be channelled to the EE Aggregator, ensuring a shorter payback period and higher attractiveness to third-party investors, while also providing a cheaper-than-the-alternatives solution for both maintaining grid stability and meeting EEO schemes targets.

Energy providers/ utilities**Description:**

Energy providers/ utilities are companies or other organizations that supply electricity or natural gas to customers. These companies do not own and operate the distribution or transmission lines. Instead, they obtain readings from DSOs and bill their customers according to those readings. Retail energy suppliers generally buy electricity from generators (owners of generation plants) in wholesale energy markets, to then resell it to their customers at a retail price [85,86].

Role:

Since electricity end users are usually not exposed to wholesale energy market prices, there might be some hours of the day when buying electricity in the wholesale market and delivering

it to their customers generates economic losses for retail energy suppliers [85]. Additionally, retail energy suppliers, depending on the EU Member State they operate in, might have to align with EEOS and achieve specific cumulative end-use energy savings, otherwise, they face monetary penalties [81,87]. Because of this situation, in certain cases, it might be cost-efficient for energy retailers to invest in efficiency upgrade measures to reduce its customers' consumption total and demand-side flexibility solutions able to reduce the required load of their customers at peak hours, rather than deliver energy while suffering an economic loss. The role of retail energy suppliers in the EE Aggregator model would be to provide financial inflow for the implementation of the demand-side flexibility and EEMs which are deemed to be beneficial for both them and their customers. Thanks to the advanced M&V techniques in use, it will be possible to target and prioritize the buildings where these strategies could be implemented, as well as the most impactful renovation measures for those buildings.

ESCO

Description:

Energy service companies (ESCOs) are companies that offer customers a range of energy performance improvement solutions that many times involve the implementation of EE or RES projects. ESCOs act as project developers, integrating project design, financing, installation, and operational elements [88]. The contracts signed between ESCOs and their customers are usually medium-long term (between seven and twenty years, depending on the implemented measures) [89], and typically have the following characteristics:

- The remuneration of ESCOs is directly tied to the energy savings achieved through the implemented measures [89,90];
- ESCOs provide a performance guarantee which is in line with the achieved energy savings, this is usually specified through an energy savings performance contract (ESPC [91] or EPC [90]);

In the project design phase, ESCOs typically present a comprehensive plan to maximize their customers' energy savings while also taking into consideration the specific requirements of each facility under analysis [92]. The energy projects are usually designed to include multiple conservation measures and to account for interactions among them.

Role:

ESCOs' role in the EE Aggregator business model is to implement EEMs in the buildings selected for the programmes. The contracts might also include an EPC agreement if it complies with the programme's framework concerning performance reporting, accountability and distribution of the financial flows. Many ESCOs can coexist in one P4P programme, as long as each follows the same P4P standards and methods. ESCOs participating in the scheme will gain the possibility of implementing standardized EE interventions in a large number of buildings.

Public authorities**Description:**

Public authorities include any government, agency, or other public administration at the national, regional or local level. In the framework of this study, we consider public authorities that are able to use/ exploit public subsidies for the implementation of EE projects [93].

Role:

Public authorities can participate in the EE Aggregator model through EE public subsidy programmes. Public authorities can use part of the public funds/ subsidies to finance the EE programme/ projects [94,95]. Advanced M&V and continuous monitoring of the EE interventions, through the EE Aggregator, can facilitate Public authorities to increase the cost-effectiveness of their programmes. Additionally, through portfolio aggregation, private investors are given the proper de-risking tools and advanced M&V techniques, thus substantial leverage of private capital can be secured through public funds.

Third party investors**Description:**

Investors are individuals or other entities (e.g., a firm or a mutual fund) who provide capital with the expectation of receiving financial returns. Investors rely on different financial instruments to earn a rate of return and achieve long-term gain. Investment funds are typically private investors for EE projects. An investment fund is a supply of capital from a group of investors that is pooled together to buy assets while each investor retains ownership and control of his or her shares. Many funds are looking to invest in socially and environmentally friendly business practices, such as RES or EE projects.

Role:

The role of external investors is to provide financing at the programme and/ or project level for the implementation of the measures that will generate EE savings from which return payments will follow. Generally, EE investments in residential buildings are not attractive for financial institutions mainly because they are characterized by a high degree of fragmentation, so there is the necessity to bundle many small investments into a larger one [96]. The aggregation helps investors manage their risk, creates economies of scale, and can unlock financing from funds that have a high minimum investment threshold. At the same time, EE projects that are part of P4P schemes enjoy shorter payback periods thanks to the possibility of leveraging public subsidies and investments from system operators and energy retailers.

End users

Description:

End users are usually building owners who are individuals or companies that have owners' rights to a property such as a block of land or building [97]. Building owners might rent or lease their property to another party in exchange for rent payments. A distinction can be made between public building owners and private building owners.

I. Public owners

This is the case of buildings owned and managed by the public sector. Typical buildings included in this category are public office buildings, social housing (residential), health centres or hospitals, penitentiary centres, museums, libraries, schools, social or sports centres, among other kinds of facilities and infrastructures.

II. Private owners

In this category three different groups are distinguished:

- **Individuals:** in general landlords of an apartment or an isolated house. This could also include neighbourhood associations, a community of homeowners, property managers.
- **Private companies:** in this group, we can find retailers, private office buildings, private schools and hospitals, commercial, industry, hotels, leisure and sports centres.
- **Energy community:** the community shareholders participate as an entity and not individually.

Role:

The main obligations and responsibilities of building owners are related to continuously sharing the necessary energy data, providing proactive feedback depending on the programme's terms and conditions, and ensuring the proper use of new facilities or implemented measures. When implementing the EE Aggregator business model, the economic and investment capacity, interest, motivation of the building owners, as well as the characteristic and energy consumption profiles of their buildings, must be considered. In the project acquisition phase, it is also important to take into account that individual private building owners present considerable barriers to the implementation of EEMs in their buildings, mainly due to the substantial initial investment required.

Public owners

Public authorities can participate in the EE Aggregator business model by having their energy-inefficient buildings retrofitted (e.g., within a P4P programme). EE requirements should be more demanding for public buildings since Public authorities must set an example to the rest of the population and define the guidelines according to the energy transition and decarbonization public policies. Public authorities manage a wide range of building typologies and uses, meaning that their retrofit can enable different demand-side flexibility solutions and grid services. It should also be considered that in some cases public authorities are not the direct owners and there might be a Building Manager (BM), who establishes mandatory strategies and guidelines for all these buildings in which it carries out public services.

Private owners

Private building owners are the landlords of buildings, dwellings or flats that present an inadequate EE performance, and as a consequence need some kind of renovation or EEMs implementation. The building owner can apply for a P4P programme, either directly, or

indirectly through another channel e.g., an ESCO, a DSO/TSO, an energy provider, or building owners association or energy community. Contractual compliance to all rules set in terms of flows of data and finance (on top of the ones described in an individual EPC contract) is required.

5.2 Interactions between the different actors

In this paragraph, the main interactions between the different actors previously introduced, are presented. The EE Aggregator is the central figure of the business model presented in this study and interacts with all the other relevant stakeholders as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Interaction between the energy efficiency aggregator and other market actors relevant to the business model

Energy efficiency aggregator – TSO/DSO

EE Aggregator have an exchange of financial and data flows with system operators [68]. System operators define the performance rates that they would be willing to pay to finance EE interventions as non-wire alternatives to avoid investment in increasing grid capacity. These performance rates can either be defined in advance or through bidding in an auction [68]. Based on these rates, system operators will be paying to the EE Aggregator fixed tariffs for the implementation of certain measures, and/or variable fees depending on

concrete events in which dispatchable flexibility is provided by the EE Aggregator through the buildings in their portfolio. The EE Aggregator channels these payments to the other relevant stakeholders and uses them to finance the implementation of EEMs or to pay back other potential investors who funded the EE project.

Energy efficiency aggregator – Energy providers/ utilities

EE Aggregators and energy providers are also connected by financial and data flows [74]. Energy retailers are interested in paying EE Aggregators at peak hours when modifying the load shape through demand-side flexibility solutions is considered to be more cost-effective than delivering electricity to their customers. EE Aggregators use the information provided by retail energy suppliers to create price signals and can channel the energy suppliers' payments to repay the initial investment required to perform the renovation. Additionally, according to EEOS, the retail energy suppliers operating in the EU are obliged to meet quantitative energy savings targets across their customer portfolio [81]. In order to increase the cost-effectiveness of the EE projects they implement, the energy retailers could participate in a P4P scheme and pay EE Aggregators to guarantee a specific amount of energy savings and implement the EE projects.

Energy efficiency aggregator – ESCOs

When creating a P4P program, one or more ESCOs will have the task of implementing the EEMs in the participant buildings. ESCOs will receive one initial payment, used to cover the upfront investment costs of the renovations, and several periodic payments based on performance, for the whole duration of the P4P program. The ESCOs will leverage their expertise, as well as the large quantity of data collected by EE Aggregators, to take insightful decisions regarding the most suitable and profitable renovations that can be implemented in the buildings selected for the program.

Energy efficiency aggregator – Public authorities

EE Aggregators will also have the task of collaborating with public authorities for the successful inclusion, whenever possible, of public subsidies in P4P programs. Public authorities with allocated budgets for EE renovations in buildings will have to coordinate with EE Aggregators to define the best strategy to leverage private capital with the available public funds. EE Aggregators perform periodic reporting to public authorities, detailing the amount of avoided energy and emissions, estimated with their advanced M&V tools. Public authorities will then provide periodic payments based on these

performance estimates. EE Aggregators will use these additional cash flows to directly finance interventions or to pay back third-party investors and building owners who paid the upfront intervention costs.

In addition to the EE Aggregator's interactions, the following relationships were also found to be relevant in the scheme:

Energy efficiency aggregator – Investors

EE Aggregators have the task of attracting third-party investors by creating a portfolio of EE interventions that reach the minimum investment threshold of the investors, while also providing the necessary risk management tools through the aggregation of individual projects. EE Aggregators will also be able to attract investors through additional financial flows, such as payments from system operators for providing permanent or dispatchable services to the grid. Investors provide the initial payment to the EE Aggregator, who uses the funds to finance the required EE interventions. The EE Aggregator then pays back the upfront investment through regular payments based on performance and the additional revenues secured from other stakeholders participating in the program. EE Aggregator will have to prove the accuracy and reliability of their M&V techniques since investor payback will be also based on the estimations of achieved savings.

Energy efficiency aggregator – Building owners

One of the tasks of EE Aggregator is also to find eligible buildings and facilities to be included in the P4P programs. In this process, the EE Aggregator will have to be in contact with building owners to understand the characteristics of the buildings they manage, the energy savings potential provided, and whether the owners would be willing to take any upfront investment cost on themselves. The EE Aggregators have to indicate to the end users possible ways to optimise their consumption behavior and encourage Building owners to aim for deep energy upgrades and not focusing on the easiest and or short-term savings to obtain. In the case of having third-party investors who financed the interventions, EE Aggregator might also have the task of collecting fees relevant to the savings obtained on the owners' energy bills. These payments will be redistributed to repay the initial investment and to pay for the services of the different entities who participate in the program (EE Aggregators, ESCOs, etc.).

ESCOs – Building owners

In a P4P program, ESCOs have to coordinate with building owners to agree on the measures which will be implemented and the logistics of the renovation work. In this discussion, building owners can bring attention to the value of increasing or at least maintaining, occupant's comfort through the chosen renovations. Comfort is a key parameter that is many times neglected when evaluating the impact of EE renovations and it is important to take it into account when performing design decisions.

Public authorities – TSO/DSO/Retail energy suppliers

Together with the allocation of public subsidies for the implementation of energy renovation strategies, PAs are usually in charge of managing EEOS. EEOS set an obligation for energy companies to achieve certain energy savings targets. Depending on the country in analysis, energy suppliers can be either directly financing measures for their customers or channelling capital into EE funds. Public entities have the authority to compel energy distributors and suppliers to participate in P4P programs as part of their EEOS.

Investors – Public authorities

Public authorities are interested in leveraging the highest possible private capital using the public funds allocated for EE. At the same time, investors see positively the participation of public authorities in a P4P program, since this provides credibility and guarantees lower investment risk. For the success of a P4P program, it's important to have a good relationship between investors and public authorities, characterized by mutual trust.

Investors – ESCOs

When implementing EE projects outside of a P4P program, ESCOs sometimes take upon themselves the risk of taking a loan, from a bank or a private investment fund, to pay for the upfront investment costs of the renovations they will implement. This means that ESCOs may have established a relationship with investors and know how to gain their trust. Individual ESCOs contracted within the P4P program, then also have the possibility of using their expertise and credibility to influence third-party investors and persuade them to finance the projects in analysis.

6 Energy efficiency aggregator’s business model

This section focuses on the development of the EE Aggregator business model. A business model aims to define a process that creates value for customers and generates profit for the actors involved in the value proposition to the customer [98]. Therefore, it is necessary to design business models that can guarantee convenient conditions for all the involved actors, especially for end-users and investors [98]. There are different methods used for developing business models. Many research studies define at first use cases, secondly define their relevant stakeholders and actors, and finally develop business scenarios and/or concepts for selected use cases [99,100]. Another used development strategy is to build business concepts through executive workshops with the main stakeholders involved [101,102]. Other studies are also describing business concepts and models via Osterwalder’s business canvas [103–106]. The common approach in analysing business and service concepts using Osterwalder’s approach is by describing the product, customer interface, infrastructure management and financial aspects in nine different subtopics displayed in the BMC.

In this work, a typological analysis is conducted and several business ‘archetypes’ are identified according to different EEA’s responsibilities, involved parties, monetary flows and financial sources, in a way that each archetype highlights its particular factors of importance. Each archetype consists of a configuration of various business model elements and aims at strengthening EEA’s overall business model, while the final business model can result from the combination of the archetypes developed. Thus, by filling in the simplified Osterwalder’s model, proposed in [107] and presented in **Table 3**, a typology of different business model ‘archetypes’ emerges. These business archetypes are described in **Section 6.1** and each archetype is visualised by showing stakeholders and their main interactions related to the business model.

Table 3. Structure of the business archetype.

Elements	Description
Title	Describe in a few words the essence of the business model archetype.
Business idea/objective	Describe in a few sentences the objective of the business model archetype.
Offer/value proposition	Describe in a few sentences the service/product offered.
Customer	Who will use the service/product?

Seller/service provider	Who will offer the service/product?
Earnings/revenue model	Who pays, where does the money come from, and what needs to be bought? Who is the owner of this business?
KPIs	Main key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of the model.
Costs and benefits	What investments are needed? What are the costs and benefits?
References	Note, if the business model/idea is studied or applied somewhere else.

The archetypes of the business model are handled as a source that will provide the necessary input for the BMC in **Section 0**. This BMC consists of 9 fundamental building elements that exhibit how the EE Aggregator aims to produce revenue and deliver value in return [18]. An illustration of an empty BMC is depicted in **Figure 9**. The special sequence of the elements and the BMC form allows an integrated and persuasive representation and provide a guideline for the design process [108].

Figure 9. The business model canvas (Source: Own illustration, based on [17])

6.1 Development of the business model archetypes for the Energy Efficiency Aggregator

Below a proposed business typology for the EEA is presented. The typology consists of five archetypes and is kept clear and simple by focusing on specific services at a time. The business archetypes considered in this study are the following:

(1) Business archetype for offering flexibility in the energy system:

Offering flexibility and balancing services to DSOs and TSOs.

(2) Business archetype for energy service providers:

ESCO expanding its services and minimising performance risks.

(3) Business archetypes for energy producers and energy companies:

- a. Utilities complying with energy efficiency obligations.
- b. Utilities exploiting EE as a resource (e.g., an EE auction/ capacity market).

(4) Business archetype for public authorities:

Achieving large-scale energy savings, minimising public spending and leveraging private funding by engaging aggregators.

(5) Business archetype for new roles:

Energy communities using energy savings the same way they sell self-produced energy.

These single business archetypes can be combined into broader service offerings and business networks resulting in a business model. For a specific business case, the selection of potential business types depends on the benefits striven, and value captured in the case. In the following sections, each of the aforementioned business archetypes is described thoroughly to clarify the interactions between the different stakeholders and the value proposition.

6.1.1 Business archetype for offering flexibility in the energy system

Despite its benefits, the integration of intermittent electricity production from RES, such as wind and PV into energy systems, is accompanied by severe balancing challenges [109]. Electricity produced by RES cannot be directly adopted to follow demand because it is weather-dependent and cannot be reliably dispatched [110]. To preserve the security and reliability of the electricity grid, TSOs and DSOs have to manage and coordinate the electricity supply and demand, especially in the peak demand periods, and to defeat grid congestion. This can be achieved by engaging end-users through demand-side sources, such as EEMs and DR schemes [111,112].

Improved demand management through EE and flexibility offers several benefits to the electric grid, including reduced power generation capacity, operation, and maintenance costs; provision of ancillary services and standing reserves for system balancing and reliability with lower costs and emissions; and avoided capital costs for transmission and

distribution equipment upgrades and voltage control. Demand management technologies can be deployed alongside energy storage to meet grid flexibility needs in a highly renewable electricity future [111]. Thus, TSOs and DSOs have more than one reason to participate in a P4P scheme and finance EE projects.

The engagement of TSOs or DSOs with an EE Aggregator in a P4P scheme is presented in **Table 4** and **Figure 10**. In this business archetype, a TSO or a DSO, or even both if they are different entities, administrate and finance the P4P programme and coordinate with the EE Aggregator to implement the EE projects. The EE Aggregator pools several projects into a portfolio of savings, collects and evaluates information about the initial efficiency state of the buildings and the consumption profiles of their end-users, elaborates the necessary EEMs according to energy savings targets and implements the renovation through ESCOs or contractors. A smart design of incentives for EE (permanently reducing energy consumption) can also lead to increased capacity for buildings to provide flexible services to the grid. Apart from the ‘pure’ EEMs, (i.e. measures that permanently reduce energy consumption), such as highly insulating windows, LED lighting, and highly efficient heating and cooling equipment, the renovation includes the installation of appliances and smart controls that allow buildings to actively manage electric loads to provide grid flexibility services while meeting occupant comfort and productivity requirements. For an agreed period after the intervention, the EE Aggregator collects the end-users new consumption data and the successful responses to DR signals from their energy suppliers compares them to a baseline weather-normalised consumption scenario and calculates the achieved savings. According to these metered savings and a performance rate (€/ kWh) agreed in advance, the administrative entity rewards the EE Aggregator through performance-based payments. Properly designed P4P incentives can both incentivize EE and improve demand flexibility, thus achieving real, measurable energy savings.

Table 4. Offering flexibility and balancing services to DSOs and TSOs.

Title	Offering flexibility and balancing services to DSOs and TSOs
Business idea/objective	The EE Aggregator pools several buildings into a project portfolio and elaborates a plan with the necessary EEM and DR equipment according to energy savings targets and flexibility impacts. For an agreed period after the implementation of the upgrade, the EE Aggregator collects the end users’ new consumption data and the

	<p>successful responses to DR signals from their energy suppliers and they then make a weather-normalised comparison and calculates the achieved savings. According to these verified savings and a performance rate (€/ kWh) agreed upon in advance, the TSO/ DSO rewards the EE Aggregator through performance-based payments for providing flexibility services.</p>
Offer/value proposition	<p>Grid benefits from reducing and shifting peak time demand, such as extra capacity and reliability for the TSO and grid balance and stability for the DSO. Increasing buildings' EE and saving energy costs. Supporting households to become self-sufficient and grid-interactive.</p> <p>Growing up-take of innovative data gathering and processing methods in the monitoring and verification of energy savings and flexibility.</p>
Customer	<p>Customers that need complete, easy and carefree energy solutions with high-quality performance in indoor conditions, energy solutions, EE, and energy management services. E.g. prosumers or other customers willing to offer their flexibility or overproduction.</p>
Seller/service provider	<p>The EE Aggregator provides EE services to the end users and assists TSOs and DSOs in preserving grid security and reliability.</p>
Earnings/revenue model	<p>EEA's earnings come from the TSO's/ DSO's reward and depend on the achieved portfolio savings (€/kWh).</p>
KPIs	<p>Economic feasibility for different stakeholders involved.</p> <p>Energy/ Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions saved due to efficiency improvements and DR actions.</p> <p>Number of customers/ services involved.</p> <p>Avoided-costs calculation (e.g., by reducing the need for power plants or batteries to supply peaks in grid demand, cutting down on grid infrastructure upgrade costs, etc.)</p>
Costs and benefits	<p>Benefits: Improvement of baseline efficiency and targeted peak-demand reductions, limitation of grid congestion due to decrease of peak demand, reduction of necessary network upgrades, reduced reserve requirements, economies of scale due to pooling of projects, simplification of the project eligibility procedure through standardisation, minimisation of performance risks</p>

through aggregation.

Costs: Initial investments in the implementation of EEMs, design costs, transaction costs, communication costs, smart appliances.

References

[111], [113], [114]

Figure 10. Stakeholder interactions for offering flexibility and balancing services to DSOs and TSOs.

6.1.2 Business archetype for energy service providers

In this section, the business archetype for energy service providers and specifically for ESCOs that are a staple in the EE market is presented. By providing EPCs, these companies can help building owners and users with an appetite for longer payback periods to finance efficiency projects through the energy savings over time, with very little upfront investment [91,92]. The EPC model has been successful in attracting investments in EE, but mainly for single, large projects where the building owners offer a large portfolio of buildings and either the ESCO is large enough to secure a loan to finance the retrofit or the building owners have the capacity to invest in their EE [115]. Such projects mainly consist of buildings from the so-called MUSH market (municipalities, universities, schools and hospitals), where ESCOs appear to be quite attractive [116]. EPCs have been very popular in the public and institutional sectors where customers are more willing to accept longer payback periods [117]. But in the commercial sector, where companies are looking for much shorter paybacks and where smaller energy service providers often lack financing, the model has not taken off [91,115].

ESCOs can expand their market reach in the commercial, residential or SME building sector by collaborating with aggregating entities that pool together buildings and manage a single contract for ESCO services to implement the EEMs in all these buildings.

According to the business archetype presented in **Table 5** and **Figure 11**, the ESCO is able to take over a portfolio of different EE projects by entering only a single EPC contract with the EEA, reducing transaction costs and limiting performance risks. The EEA pools the different projects into a portfolio, evaluates them and aggregates their consumption behaviour. After the efficiency intervention, the EE Aggregator has to perform M&V in order to calculate the achieved savings and reward the ESCO accordingly.

Table 5. ESCO expanding its services and minimising performance risks.

Title	ESCO expanding its services and minimising performance risks.
Business idea/objective	The ESCO enters into a single EPC contract with the EE Aggregator for a whole portfolio of buildings and guarantees an aggregated amount of savings for the whole portfolio and not for each building, thus minimizing performance risks. ESCO performs the EE renovations of all buildings of the portfolio and then, the EE Aggregator measures and verifies the amount of total achieved savings and rewards the ESCO accordingly.
Offer/value proposition	The aggregated commercial, residential buildings and SME buildings can be upgraded by ESCOs through an EPC - P4P scheme even if the building owners cannot invest in EE upgrades. The ESCO benefits from the reduction of transaction costs – a single EPC for a portfolio of projects, the EEM cost advantage due to pooling of projects and the minimization of the performance by guaranteeing the total savings. Investors benefit from the guaranteed revenues of the EE investment.
Customer	Occupant owners who want to reduce their energy consumption, increase their comfort and well-being and add more value to their buildings. SMEs/ commercial buildings who want to reduce their energy consumption and add more value to their buildings. Minimising the costs for the customers and optimising their energy usage.
Seller/service provider	The EEA, who creates the building portfolio, measures and verifies achieved savings and rewards the ESCO for savings

	achieved.
Earnings/revenue model	An investor makes the upfront investment to finance the EE interventions. The source of EEA's earnings is the in advance agreed revenues per metered energy savings (€/ KWh for electricity or €/ m3 for natural gas) from the efficiency upgrade.
KPIs	Energy/ GHG emissions saved due to efficiency improvements, Economic feasibility for different stakeholders involved, Number of customers/ services involved, Percentage of customers that choose deep energy upgrades.
Costs and benefits	Benefits: Minimising performance risks, maximising energy savings, and increasing the cost-effectiveness of EEMs. Through the EE Aggregator the ESCO can also collaborate with other actors, e.g., utilities, DSOs, etc. and leverage funding from additional sources. Costs: Transaction costs, communication costs
References	[88], [117], [89], [90]

Figure 11. Stakeholder interactions for ESCO maximising energy savings and minimising performance risks.

6.1.3 Business archetypes for energy producers and energy companies

Regarding the energy producers and energy companies, i.e. utilities, two main business typologies may be distinguished; “Utilities complying with energy efficiency obligations”

and “*Utilities exploiting EE as a resource (e.g., through an EE auction/ capacity market)*”.

EEOS are legislative mechanisms that place requirements on “Obligated Parties” (OPs) to meet quantitative energy savings targets across -and sometimes beyond- their customer basis. OPs may be utilities, energy distributors, transport fuel distributors, and/or transport fuel retailers and energy suppliers [118]. In Europe, the energy savings requirement under Article 7 was introduced by the 2012 EE Directive, initially only for the 2014-2020 period, when the Member States had to achieve 1.5% annual energy savings. With the 2018 revision of the EE Directive, Article 7 was extended beyond 2020, and the Member States are implementing for the 2021-2030 period [119]. Following the introduction of the EU EE Directive in 2012 the number of EEOS in Europe has grown from five schemes to now 16 EEOS in operation [81]. P4P programmes that use the energy EE Aggregator business model have been mainly implemented by utilities in the USA in the context of EE Resource Standards, which are the respective obligations for OPs in the USA. Regulations in the US often obligate utilities to offer and administrate programmes in order to deliver energy savings and support the grid. In addition, in many cases, for example in California, state energy laws require innovative pilots and programmes to be applied to ensure the cost-effectiveness of these schemes funded by rate-payers. Thus, as the schemes that have been already in place, utilities in obligation schemes can deliver some of their targets using the P4P approach to increase the cost-effectiveness of the EE projects they implement. In countries or states where there are capacity mechanisms, P4P pilots could be applied in the context of the Efficiency First principle [120].

To increase their economic feasibility, the utilities have to maximize the overall savings that an EE upgrade project can produce and minimise the risk of implementing EEMs that will not produce the planned savings. In the “*Utilities complying with energy efficiency obligations*” business archetype, the EE Aggregator pools a portfolio of utility’s end users’ buildings, uses information about the current efficiency state of the buildings and the consumption profiles of their end-users, evaluates this information, elaborates the suitable EEMs and implements the retrofit. After the intervention, the EE Aggregator measures the end-users' new consumption data, makes a weather-normalised comparison and calculates the achieved savings. The EE Aggregator is rewarded by the utility,

according to the achieved amount of savings, so the performance risks are transferred from the utility to the EEA. This business type is presented in **Table 6** and **Figure 12**.

Table 6. Utilities complying with energy efficiency obligations

Title	Utilities complying with energy efficiency obligations.
Business idea/objective	<p>The utility has to achieve specific end-use energy savings to comply with the EEOS. The EE Aggregator pools a portfolio of selected buildings that are customers of the utility. Furthermore, the EE Aggregator elaborates the necessary EEMs according to consumption information and the end-use energy savings targets, and implements EE upgrades, possibly through contractors and ESCOs. For a performance period after the efficiency intervention, the EE Aggregator monitors the energy consumption of the upgraded buildings and calculates and verifies the achieved savings. The utility rewards the EE Aggregator for these savings according to performance rate (e.g €/kWh). If the targets are achieved, the responsible authority for the EEO scheme validates the EE claim and does not impose any penalty on the utility.</p>
Offer/value proposition	<p>The utilities take over efficiency projects to comply with the EEOS, without facing the risk of financing a low-performance project. The EE Aggregator is reimbursed based on the savings achieved and thus tries to minimize the performance risks. All savings are verified thus increasing the cost-effectiveness of the EE projects and ensuring a successful outcome.</p> <p>The buildings of the portfolio are renovated even if the building owners cannot pay the full upfront cost of the EE measures.</p>
Customer	<p>Occupant owners who want to reduce their energy consumption, increase their comfort and well-being and add more value to their buildings. SMEs who want to reduce their energy consumption and add more value to their buildings.</p>
Seller/service provider	<p>The EEA, who creates the building portfolio out of utility's customers, evaluates the consumption behaviour and portfolio information to elaborate the most efficient EEMs, implements the EEMs (possibly through contractors), measures the post-intervention consumption, calculates and verifies aggregated achieved savings.</p>

Earnings/revenue model	The earnings of the EE Aggregator come from the utility according to the metered savings from the EE upgrades and the performance rate agreed (€/kWh or €/ kWh).
KPIs	Percentage of the EE targets achieved as part of the EEOs, Energy/ GHG emissions saved due to efficiency improvements, Number of customers/ services involved, Percentage of customers that chose deep energy upgrades.
Costs and benefits	<p>Benefits: Increased cost-effectiveness for ratepayers, innovation in the EE market, limitation of grid congestion due to total demand reduction, reduction of necessary network upgrades, reduced reserve requirements, economies of scale due to pooling of projects, simplification of the project eligibility procedure through standardisation, minimisation of performance risks through aggregation</p> <p>Costs: Transaction costs, communication costs, installation of smart meters and smart infrastructure</p>
References	[87], [121]

Figure 12. Utilities complying with EE obligations.

Capacity markets are often established by load-serving entities (e.g., DSOs, TSOs, etc.) to ensure that adequate capacity will be able to meet load, including during peak periods. However, where they are in place, EE is often excluded either explicitly or implicitly (because of participation rules) from participating [120]. There are already successful examples of using efficiency as a capacity resource in forwarding capacity auctions in the

USA, and there is considerable scope for allowing EE to bid into capacity markets in the EU. Assuming that energy providers are both willing and able to take EE to markets that can monetise it, P4P schemes can act as the vehicle for compensating EE as an energy resource. In this approach, the administrative entity will enter into agreements with EE Aggregators or building owners to purchase the metered EE being delivered based on the value to the utility [122]. Using smart meter data, it is possible to track results including time and location and value a distributed resource called demand capacity that looks very similar to other DERs. This approach could also create a cash flow based on the grid benefit that allows private capital markets to invest in EE through project finance, similar to other grid infrastructure investments [112,123].

In the “*Utilities exploiting energy efficiency as a resource*” business archetype, the EE Aggregator pools a building portfolio of a utility’s end users, uses information about the current efficiency state of the buildings and the consumption profiles of their end-users, evaluates this information, and elaborates the suitable EEMs. Then, the EEA, alone or through contractors and ESCOs, undertakes the implementation of the efficiency measures, and at the same time, the utility bids in the capacity market the future estimated savings that these EEMs will bring, and is obliged to deliver them in time. After the intervention, the EE Aggregator measures the end-users' new consumption data, compares them to a baseline weather-normalised consumption scenario and calculates the achieved savings. In case of successful delivery (i.e. delivery of a specific amount of capacity and at a specific time, both determined by the competitive auction), the EE Aggregator is rewarded by the utility, according to the measured and verified savings of the portfolio (€/kWh for electricity or €/ m³ for natural gas upgrade) and the utility is rewarded by the capacity market through a stream of performance payments at a price determined by the competitive auction. This business type is presented in **Table 7** and **Figure 13**.

Table 7. Utilities exploiting energy efficiency as a resource.

Title	Utilities exploiting energy efficiency as a resource (e.g. an energy efficiency auction/ capacity market).
Business idea/objective	The EE Aggregator pools a portfolio of utility’s end users’ buildings, evaluates them, elaborates the suitable EEMs and implements the upgrade. At the same time, the utility bids in the capacity market the future estimated savings due to these EEMs

	<p>and is obliged to deliver them in time. After the intervention, the EEA, measures the end users' new consumption data, makes a weather-normalised comparison and calculates the achieved savings. In case of a successful upgrade, the EEA is rewarded by the utility, according to the measured and verified savings of the portfolio (€/kWh or €/ m³ natural gas) and the utility receives payment according to the market-clearing price.</p>
Offer/value proposition	<p>EE upgrade for the buildings of utility's end users. EE competes with supply-side investments. Valorisation of EE by mitigating the need for ramping reserves to address the “duck curve” effect of solar power over generation and other system peaks. Grid benefits through private finance. Opportunity for the utility to participate in the EE auction and achieve part of its energy savings target by bidding in EE.</p>
Customer	<p>The utility that finances the efficiency upgrade to deliver the bidden in the capacity market amount of EE.</p> <p>Occupant owners who want to reduce their energy consumption, increase their comfort and well-being and add more value to their buildings. SMEs who want to reduce their energy consumption and add more value to their buildings. The public sector wants to decarbonize buildings through innovative approaches. The buildings of all the above building owners must be end-users of the energy services of the utility.</p>
Seller/service provider	<p>The EE Aggregator provides EE services to the utility to bid in the capacity market absorbing the underperformance risk.</p>
Earnings/revenue model	<p>EEA's earnings come from the utility's reward and depend on the achieved portfolio savings (€/kWh or €/ m³).</p>
KPIs	<p>Delivery precision in schedule and EE objectives, Total reduction of non-coincident peak demand, Total reduction of energy consumption, Limitation of the requests for ancillary services and standing reserves for system balancing, Energy saved due to efficiency improvements</p>
Costs and benefits	<p>Benefits: Innovation in the EE market, limitation of grid congestion due to total demand reduction, limitation of costly capacity levels, reduction of necessary network upgrades, reduced reserve requirements, avoided CO₂ permit costs for power</p>

generating facilities, economies of scale due to pooling of projects, simplification of the project eligibility procedure through standardisation, minimisation of performance risks through aggregation

Costs: Installation of smart meters and smart infrastructures, design costs, transaction costs, communication costs,

References

[123], [112]

Figure 13. Utilities exploiting energy efficiency as a resource.

6.1.4 Business archetype for public authorities

The climate crisis demands that public authorities lead the energy transition in both policy and practice. The necessity and urgency of government leadership in this area are reflected in Article 5 of the EED, which emphasizes the exemplary role of public buildings. This article requires, that each member state ensures that at least 3% of the floor area of buildings owned by public bodies are renovated every year up to nearly zero energy building (NZEB) standard. Since they are frequently visited by the public, public buildings contribute to raising awareness and must lead the way by example in achieving a high level of energy performance. The diversity of public buildings also means that they are a microcosm of what will need to happen in other building segments and as such play a key role in preparing the market for wider uptake. However, the public sector usually participates in EE projects either through public subsidy policies or EPC schemes. Subsidy policies often rely on pre-assumed (deemed) savings so they could lead to

inadequate performing renovations and unachieved savings. EPC schemes that guarantee the planned energy savings are mostly suitable only for large projects excluding smaller buildings from the renovation processes [98]. To act as a role model public authorities should go beyond traditional financing mechanisms and engage with the private sector through innovative business models.

An EE Aggregator business model archetype that engages public authorities and public organisations is described below. Several public authorities can participate in this business archetype with a variety of responsibilities. Every country has its own structure of public sector with different offices, services and organisations, So in order to keep the archetype as generic as it can be, in the following analysis, the term public authority stands for a variety of authorities or public organisations.

In the “*Achieving large-scale energy savings, minimising public spending and leveraging private funding by engaging aggregators*” business archetype the public authority is the programme owner, so it is its responsibility to produce the necessary regulatory framework and administrative procedures that enable all interested actors to participate. Also, it has to develop the necessary communication channels between the stakeholders and regulate their connection and cooperation procedures efficiently, clarify the cash flows, design the programme, delimit its bounds, draw up the guidelines and create the mechanisms to check if the expected results are obtained. After the programme kicks off, the public authority publishes an RFP and each EE Aggregator pools a building portfolio, uses information about the current efficiency state of the buildings and the consumption profiles of their end users, evaluates this information, and elaborates specific EEMs about the efficiency upgrade of these buildings. In case of acceptance, the tendering public authority builds a contractual agreement with the EE Aggregator at the portfolio level and the EE Aggregator attracts investors to leverage private funds because public money is insufficient for multiple renovation projects [98] and enters into an agreement with ESCOs or other contractors to implement the efficiency upgrade. The EE Aggregator monitors the energy consumption of the portfolio buildings, both before and after the intervention, and makes a weather-normalised comparison according to the M&V protocol in order to calculate the achieved cumulative savings on an ongoing basis. The EE Aggregator is rewarded through several performance-based payments according to both these savings and a performance rate (€/ kWh electric or thermal) agreed in advance by the end users and the public authority and rewards the contractors according to their

agreement and the third-party investors according to the achieved savings. Apart from reducing energy consumption from public buildings, the public authority minimises public spending by rewarding the EE Aggregator only for verified savings and by using also third-party financing. This business type is presented in **Table 8** and **Figure 14**.

Table 8. Achieving large-scale energy savings, minimising public spending and leveraging private funding by engaging aggregators.

Title	Achieving large-scale energy savings, minimising public spending and leveraging private funding by engaging aggregators.
Business idea/objective	The public authority designs and coordinates the P4P program and enters into a contractual agreement with the EE Aggregator for a building portfolio. The EE Aggregator attract investors to finance the retrofits, elaborates the EEM according to the efficiency state of each building and the energy consumption of the end users and enters into agreements with contractors to implement the EE retrofit. After the intervention, the EE Aggregator monitors end users' consumption and calculates and verifies the achieved energy savings. According to these savings and a performance rate (€/ KWh or €/ m3), the EE Aggregator is rewarded by the end users and the public authority on a regular basis, and then rewards the contractors and investors according to their agreement.
Offer/value proposition	EE upgrade of small buildings that normally are not preferred in pure EPC schemes, the cost-effectiveness of public spending and verified achieved savings ensuring that targets related to public authorities and public buildings are on track.
Customer	The public sector can achieve large-scale energy savings and minimise public spending, increase the well-being of citizens using or working in public buildings and become a frontrunner in the decarbonisation of the building sector. Private building owners, of either dwellings or SME buildings, want to add more value to their buildings, reduce their energy consumption and increase their comfort and well-being through programmes that are organised by public authorities.
Seller/service provider	The EEA, which enters into contractual agreements with the public authority and the contractors, pools multiple buildings into

	a portfolio, elaborates the EEMs, monitors the consumption and verifies the energy savings and absorbs the risk of underperforming renovations.
Earnings/revenue model	EEA's earnings come from the building owners and the public authority and depend on the achieved portfolio savings (€/kWh or €/ m3), after deducting the contractors' rewards and the profits of the investors.
KPIs	Percentage of the EE targets achieved, Economic feasibility of stakeholders, Energy saved due to efficiency improvements, Number of small public buildings and dwellings involved, Percentage of private building owners that chose deep energy upgrades.
Costs and benefits	Benefits: Simplification of the project eligibility procedure through standardisation, Minimisation of performance risks through aggregation, Limitation of initial costs for the portfolio creation and management Costs: Design costs, transaction costs, communication costs, contractors' reward
References	[68]

Figure 14. Achieving large-scale energy savings, minimising public spending and leveraging private funding by engaging aggregators.

6.1.5 Business archetype for new roles

Global efforts to mitigate the climate crisis and meet the decarbonisation goals require the participation of new actors, such as prosumers and energy communities, in the power system. Energy communities are non-commercial entities that, although engaged in economic activity, have as a primary purpose to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits and not to prioritise profit-making [124]. Their main activities include generation, supply, consumption and energy sharing, distribution (electricity and heating networks), storage of energy and provision of energy-related services, electromobility and financial services [124,125]. The concept of prosumerism enables individual end-users to both consume and generate power, either for self-consumption or consumption by others [126]. Furthermore, organised collectively, energy communities engage with local households, enable local citizen participation and raise social acceptance for the energy transition [127]. Although, there are several business models based on renewable energy and self-consumption schemes, business models involving differentiated services such as demand flexibility, aggregation, energy efficiency and electric mobility are still scarce in energy communities [128].

However, there are already energy communities interested in EE [124], providing measures to improve renovation of buildings and promoting energy auditing and consumption monitoring as well as heating and air quality assessments [124,129]. The business archetype of this subsection describes how energy communities could participate in EE projects through the EE Aggregator business model.

The fact that energy communities are already aggregated entities simplifies the P4P scheme and facilitates the EEA's efforts to attract building owners. According to this, the *"Energy communities using energy savings the same way they sell self-produced energy"* business archetype is described below and presented in **Table 9** and **Figure 15**. The EE Aggregator enters into a single agreement with the community and pools buildings of the community shareholders into a portfolio, instead of managing a group of independent building owners. The EE Aggregator collects the consumption profiles of the end-users from their energy supplier for a sufficient period before the upgrade, evaluates them considering the initial efficiency state of their residential buildings and implements specific EEMs. In order to implement the upgrade, the EE Aggregator enters either into an EPC scheme with ESCO(s) (such as in Section 6.1.2) or into another form of agreement with contractors. The initial fund for this investment derives from an energy provider/

utility or a third-party investor. For a specific period after the intervention, the energy supplier provides the EE Aggregator with end-use consumption measurements of the portfolio buildings, the EE Aggregator compares them with a weather-normalised scenario of the consumption before the upgrade according to M&V protocols and calculates the accumulative achieved savings for the whole portfolio. During this specific period, the community regularly rewards the EE Aggregator according to the accumulative achieved energy savings and a performance rate (€/kWh or €/ m³ of natural gas). The EE Aggregator has to reward the contractors according to their contractual agreement. The energy supplier, apart from trading the generated electricity, also compensates the community for these achieved savings regularly, as an additional energy resource.

Table 9. Energy communities using energy savings the same way they sell self-produced energy

Title	Energy communities using energy savings the same way they sell self-produced energy
Business idea/objective	The EE Aggregator creates a portfolio with the buildings of the community shareholders, evaluates their efficiency state and their consumption behaviour and enters into a form of agreement with ESCO(s) or other contractors to perform the efficiency upgrade. For a performance period, the EE Aggregator monitors the consumption of portfolio buildings and measures and verifies the achieved amount of savings. The energy supplier compensates the community for the efficient performance and the community compensates the EE Aggregator according to the achieved saving regularly. The latter rewards the contractors for the EE renovation according to their contractual agreements.
Offer/value proposition	Reduced energy bills for the community's shareholders due to more efficient buildings. Extra profit for the community from trading EE as an energy resource. Opportunity for the energy supplier to bid for efficiency in the capacity market or to align with EEOS (see subsection 6.1.3).
Customer	The energy community that participates in the P4P scheme in order to trade efficiency achieved as an additional energy resource.
Seller/service provider	The EEA, who creates the portfolio, processes the EEMs, enters

	into contractual agreements with contractors to implement the upgrade, and is rewarded according to the measured performance of the upgrade.
Earnings/revenue model	The EE Aggregator rewards the contractors according to their agreements and is rewarded by the community according to the accumulative achieved energy savings and the performance rate (€/kWh or €/ m3). Initial costs of the EE upgrade are covered either by the EE Aggregator or a third-party investor.
KPIs	Community's profits from trading EE, Energy/ GHG emissions saved due to efficiency improvements, The economic feasibility of stakeholders involved, especially in the case of third-party investor
Costs and benefits	Benefits: Limitation of initial costs for the portfolio creation and management, EEM cost advantage due to pooling of projects, Minimisation of performance risks through aggregation Costs: Design costs, Transaction Costs, Communication Costs, Contractors' rewards
References	[130], [131], [132]

Figure 15. Energy communities using energy savings the same way they sell self-produced energy.

6.2 The Business Model Canvas

In this section, the business model of an EE Aggregator is defined by the nine fundamental elements of the BMC. The main material to fill the BMC comes from the typology of Section 6.1 and the case studies of Sections 4.1 and 4.2. Initially, every section of the BMC is described thoroughly in the following paragraphs and then this information is summarized as a BMC in **Table 10**.

- Key Partners:** The key public partners of an EE Aggregator as noted in previous archetypes. The DSO(s), utilities, electricity/ gas distributors and retail sellers provide the EE Aggregator with the necessary energy consumption measurements of the end-users. The ESCOs or other contractors are designing and implementing the EE renovation. The third-party investors finance the whole projects and expect profit. The public authorities create the necessary legal and regulatory framework and administrative procedures in order for the business model to be operational.

Some of them, are also receiving a service from the EE Aggregator so they are also included in the Customer Segments block.

- **Customer Segments:** Non-occupant owners who want to add more value to their buildings. Occupant owners who want to reduce their energy consumption, increase their comfort and well-being and add more value to their buildings. SMEs who want to reduce their energy consumption and add more value to their buildings. Energy communities/ PrCs who trade the increased efficiency as an additional energy resource. The public sector, wants to achieve large-scale energy savings in order to minimise public spending and to lead and promote the decarbonisation of the building sector. The TSOs are interested in increasing the capacity and reliability of the grid without further infrastructure investment. The DSO(s), utilities, electricity/ gas distributors and retail sellers who want to achieve grid balance and stability by reducing and shifting peak time demand, align with the EEO schemes and bid on EE savings in the capacity market.
- **Key Activities:** Before the renovation, the EE Aggregator invites building owners and pools the projects into a portfolio, applies the portfolio proposal, attracts private investors, monitors the end-use consumption of the portfolio buildings and the weather conditions, evaluates the EE state of each building, designs a specific plan of EEM and enters into specific agreements with ESCOs and other contactors. After the renovation, the EE Aggregator monitors the consumption of the portfolio end users and performs a weather-normalised analysis to calculate the performance of the EE renovation and the achieved savings at a building and portfolio level.
- **Value Proposition:** The EE Aggregator provides EE services in an aggregated manner so the building owner is not overcharged by transaction costs. The EE Aggregator is rewarded according to measured and verified savings and thus absorbs the risk of underperforming upgrades and facilitates financiers (utilities, system operators or third-party investors) and/ or the building owners to invest in EE projects.
- **Cost Structures:** In this business model, the EE Aggregator has to afford the following costs. The EE Aggregator has to attract building owners and investors and persuade them to participate in EEA's business. For this reason, the EE

Aggregator organises dissemination campaigns to reach building owners and employs negotiation experts and financial analysts to persuade investors. Also, the EE Aggregator has to create a complicated and robust communication network because monetary flows and information transfer between all the engaged parties are highly required in EEA's business. The EE Aggregator has to employ energy experts and analysts to evaluate the EE state of the portfolio buildings and in partnership with ESCOs design the most energy-saving EEMs before the renovation and then conduct the weather-normalised analysis to calculate and verify the performance of the EE upgrade. Additionally, in order to implement the upgrade, the EE Aggregator has to engage contractors, reward them according to their agreement and direct financing from investors towards the purchase of the necessary equipment, appliances smart meters and smart infrastructures. Transaction costs for applying proposals to tendering public authorities and aligning with the regulatory framework.

- **Customer Relationships:** The EE Aggregator provides automated service to the building owners, meaning that apart from participating in EEA's business activities and purchasing its services, they are not required to interact with EEAs. The relationship between EE Aggregators and building owners starts when the latter is reached by the EE Aggregator and lasts only until the performance period is over. The DSOs, utilities, energy distributors and retail sellers, transport fuel distributors, and/or transport fuel retailers apart from being customers and financiers, also provide EE Aggregators with the energy consumption behaviour of the end-users regularly, so the relationship between them is much more interactive. This is also a long-term relationship, as they can be involved more than once, in more than one portfolio.
- **Revenue Streams:** The EEA's revenues come from the building owners or the utilities on a regular basis according to the achieved savings and a performance rate (€/ KWh for electricity or €/ m³ for natural gas) and from the one-off funding of the third-party investor.
- **Channels:** In order to attract customers, the EE Aggregator must create communication channels to reach them. Some common communication channels are the operation of a call centre with personal assistants to guide the possible

customers, the intense activity on social media, a well-designed website and a strong presence with advertisement in press and television.

- **Key Resources:** In order to operate its business activities, the EE Aggregator must possess some essential resources. Regarding human ones, these are the financial and energy experts who will persuade the investors, design the EEMs and calculate energy savings. Regarding technological ones, these are the communication network infrastructures between the interacting stakeholders and the computational software that will model energy consumption and calculate the real savings. Regarding financial ones, the EE Aggregator must have access to external funding in order to cover the required costs.

Table 10. The Business Model Canvas for the Energy Efficiency Aggregator

Key Partners	Key activities	Value Proposition	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
DSO(s), utilities, Electricity and gas distributors and retail sellers, ESCOs, investors, public authorities	Pool the building portfolio, Elaborate EEMs, Monitor the end-use consumption and calculate savings, aggregation	Limitation of the transaction costs of the EE upgrade, EE investment without the risks of underperforming upgrades, distribution of costs and responsibilities	Automated service, project-level (short-term) relationship with the building owners. Interacting and long-term relationship for the DSOs, utilities, electricity/ gas distributors and retail sellers.	DSOs, utilities, electricity/ gas distributors and retail sellers, MUSH, households, SMEs, public entities, energy communities
	Key Resources		Channels	
	Financial/ energy experts and analysts, communication infrastructures, computational software, access to fundings, public incentives, regulatory framework		One stop shops, Calling center, Personal assistants, Social media, Website, Press, face-to-face meetings	

Cost Structures	Revenue Streams
Dissemination campaigns, Experts' reward, Contractors' reward, Communication costs, Purchase of equipment and appliances, Transaction costs, procurement costs, public grid usage costs, capital costs for building and installing assets, technical and economic feasibility studies, planning costs	One-off funding from investors Regular payments per KWh or therms saved from building owners and utilities

7 Stakeholders' perceptions towards the EE Aggregator concept

To complement our BMC analysis, we conducted a two-round stakeholder consultation process to collect feedback and insights from key experts from the energy efficiency field. In the first round (Phase I: Online collaborative workshop), energy efficiency experts were invited to participate in a workshop to discuss the extension of the EPCs from the commercial to the residential sector. The feasibility of the EE Aggregator business model was among the topics discussed during the workshop. In the second round (Phase II: EU-wide online survey) an online survey was structured, which was distributed to all interested parties across the EU through the SENSEI project's communication channels.

7.1 Online workshop outcomes

The online workshop entitled “*From commercial to residential: extending Energy Performance Contracts*” was conducted on the 18th of March 2022. The workshop was organised by three H2020 projects, frESCO, Ambience and SENSEI and 32 people attended the workshop the whole time, while 255 people joined the workshop in total at different times. Participants included members of municipal institutions for promoting energy sustainable development, ESCO companies, as well as energy consulting companies and researchers working in the energy efficiency field. The workshop was divided in six sections: i) Market and regulatory framework, ii) Strategies to promote energy efficiency and reduce costs of the energy transition in residential sector, iii) Emerging business models and actors, iv) Risks and opportunities, v) Polls and Q&A session and v) Conclusions.

In the first section the current market and regulatory framework for EPCs and the residential sector was presented. In the second section the pay-back-period and other financing details about the EPC concept in the residential sector were explained to the participants. In the third section the business models developed by each project were presented, including the business model of the EE Aggregator. And finally, the risk and opportunities of each business model were discussed. Then there was a dedicated session on Q&A and different polls allowing participants to express their thoughts and ideas freely. At the same time, knowledge from different sectors was shared, which facilitated further discussion. Based on the needs and resources of each sector, participants provided their opinions on how to overcome the barriers, use the resources, and apply the business models.

In order to facilitate the discussion researchers from the three projects collaborated and developed a survey and discussed both the results and the questions with the workshop participants. The questionnaire was implemented with the ‘EUsurvey’ tool and is included in **Error! Reference source not found.**

The initial focus of the survey questions was to determine the perception of different stakeholders with regards to the constraints of the residential sector and the aggregation of smaller projects. Therefore, respondents were asked to answer multiple choice questions and questions using importance scale in order to indicate their opinion.

The results from sixteen (16) responses provided in March 2022 when the survey came online are presented below.

Figure 16. Percentage of the main initiatives that ESCOs and aggregators can facilitate in operating in the residential sector according to the survey participants. Survey responses in total figures (n=16).

Figure 17. Percentage of the main benefits of grouping small end users/projects into larger bundles according to the survey participants. Survey responses in total figures (n=16).

Figure 18. Percentage of the main barriers/ risks when aggregating energy upgrade projects according to the survey participants. Survey responses in total figures (n=16).

Figure 19. Percentage of the main market stakeholders that are currently able to aggregate the savings and the flexibility from large numbers of building renovation projects according to the survey participants. Survey responses in total figures (n=16).

The results of the analysis show that most of the participants consider that innovative financing schemes such as on-bill programmes, pay-for-performance programmes, etc. can facilitate ESCOs and aggregators in operating in the residential sector. Furthermore, grouping smaller projects into a large portfolio is seen as the second most important factor affecting the participation of these actors in residential projects. However, inefficient administrative procedures and complexity (because of the many actors and users involved) are perceived as important barriers and constraints for the aggregation of smaller EE projects. Finally, the participants stated that utilities and real estate companies are the ones currently able to group large number of small projects.

After completing the presentations and showing the results of the survey to the participants, the speakers engaged in discussion with the participants to extract key conclusions for each business model. The conclusions are targeted to each business model and were listed in four different categories i) Market and regulatory framework, ii) Strategies to promote energy efficiency and reduce costs of the energy transition in the residential sector, iii) Emerging business models and actors and iv) Risks and Opportunities. The conclusions are summarised in **Appendix B**.

7.2 EU-wide online survey results

The second round of the stakeholder consultation process included an EU-wide online survey to get feedback from a larger sample of experts and interested parties and gain data for statistical analysis. The objective of the survey was to provide a better understanding of the following questions:

- What kind of services are expected from the EE Aggregator business model?
- What are the expected benefits when using the EE Aggregator business model?
- What are the possible barriers and risks hindering the implementation of the EE Aggregator business model?

We designed the survey in the “Microsoft Forms” platform as a quantitative questionnaire, which built on the preliminary findings of our BCM analysis and the Workshop conclusions. The survey questionnaire contained mandatory and optional questions and we applied a variety of question formats, from single and multiple choice (respondents chose between multiple given answers, e.g., select the most relevant or correct statement, etc.) to Likert-like scales (respondents had to rank the importance of the different factors, e.g., from “not important” to “very important”). All responses were quantitative (e.g., rating of importance, etc.), and have been anonymised. The questionnaire is included in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Our survey population was based on a non-probability sampling– meaning it was sent via various channels to potentially interested stakeholders. In total, the survey was distributed among national, European, and international organisations and representatives from politics, business/ industry and science. We used a diverse set of private and public distribution channels, including:

- Emailing established stakeholder contacts and SENSEI consortium networks.
- Emailing the SENSEI Community, a database of stakeholders interested in the project’s news and results (the database has approximately 100 subscribers).
- Emailing SENSEI’s sister projects. We requested partners further distribute the survey.
- Sharing through the project’s/ partners’ websites and social media (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.).

The preliminary results³ from twenty nine (29) responses provided in within the period May 2022 - September 2022 are presented below. On the demographics of the respondents (**Figure 20**): The majority of the survey participants belong to Academia and research organisations (45%), while the second leading group is participants working in energy consulting (24%). Stakeholders from thirteen (13) countries participated in the survey, most of them living in Greece (32%), Spain (14%) and Belgium (14%).

³ Additional analysis is foreseen in the context of scientific publications of the SENSEI project.

Figure 20. Demographics of the survey respondents: a) In which stakeholder group do you belong? b) In which country are you living?

Figure 21. Responses of the survey participants regarding their familiarity with the EE Aggregator business model.

According to **Figure 21**, **59%** of the participants either have never heard of the EE Aggregator business model or they have only heard about it through the SENSEI project.

Figure 22. Responses of the survey participants regarding the services they would like to receive from the Energy Efficiency Aggregator.

Preliminary results of the analysis show that over 65% of the participants would like the EE Aggregator to serve as the M&V provider and aggregate energy savings into a portfolio (Figure 22). The second most important service is about aggregating energy efficiency projects, which counts for 55 % of the participants. In this case, the EE

Aggregator would not only aggregate energy savings but also the financing of the projects would be administered as a joint portfolio. The least wanted service by the EE Aggregator would be the communication and coordination among stakeholders, according to approx. 30% of the participants.

Figure 23. Responses of the survey participants regarding the limitation that could hinder the implementation of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model.

The majority of the survey participants (72%) according to **Figure 23** agree that lack of knowledge (e.g., benefits, available schemes in the market, etc.) is the greatest limitations regarding the EE Aggregator business model. Furthermore, the lack of acceptance of innovative mechanisms and the lack of standardized methods and market participation rules are two more factors that can hinder the implementation of the EEA. Unfavourable cost allocations (24%) and the current policy and market framework (28%) are the factors that are seen as less hindering regarding the implementation of the model.

Figure 24. Responses of the different benefits that can be offered by the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model as rated by the survey participants.

On a Likert-like scale of 1 (“Not important”) to 5 (“Very important”) respondents were asked to rank the importance of different benefits of the EE Aggregator business model (Figure 24). Reaching new sectors (e.g., the residential) was classified as the most important, followed by integrating multiple services such as flexibility, storage, thermal comfort, etc. Reducing energy consumption and increasing the well-being of the users and reducing the uncertainty of energy savings were also benefits highlighted as important by the participants. Finally, reducing grid expansion costs and complying with energy efficiency obligations were rated as the least expected benefits by participants.

8 Discussion and Conclusions

To achieve the decarbonization of the building sector, it is necessary to implement renovation projects and energy efficiency programmes which imply relevant financial investments. Public resources are not enough to develop these programmes; therefore, it is pivotal to attract private investments. To stimulate the investment of private capital in the energy efficiency market it is necessary to develop adequate business models which provide a solid framework for investing. In addition, as noted by Bianco and Sonvilla [98], investments for energy efficiency especially in residential buildings are characterized by a high level of fragmentation which is not attractive for financial institutions and there is the necessity to bundle many small investments into a larger one.

The business model of the EE Aggregator can facilitate the energy upgrades in the building sector and especially in the dispersed SMEs and residential buildings. An EE Aggregator, similar to DR aggregators and VPPs, can have different functions and roles including attracting customers, aggregating a sufficient number of buildings into an energy savings portfolio, monitoring and evaluating the criteria for joining and selecting the projects, looking for investors and defining the EE programme. Up to our knowledge, the existing literature about the EE Aggregator and its business models is currently scarce. Initially, this report studied the role of aggregators in the energy sector as recorded in existing literature. Regarding specifically the EEA, two case studies that were implemented in the USA were studied to highlight the way an EE Aggregator is participating in multiple energy upgrade projects and the service/value provided. The aforementioned literature review and the two case studies were essential in order to identify key information for the stakeholder analysis and the business model development. The stakeholder analysis has been structured around three main stakeholder groups - the end users and building owners, the service providers, and the regulators - and mapped the main relationships between them. The **end users** and **building owners** group includes tenants, occupant owners, energy/ prosumer communities, SMEs and the public sector. The **service providers** include the EEA, ESCOs, energy retail suppliers, the DSO and TSO, third-party investors, while the **regulators** include legislative authorities, policymakers, tendering and auditing authorities. Among all these influencing stakeholders, a web questionnaire was carried out to find out their perspective regarding

the EE Aggregator concept and their needs, goals and roles in the energy business. Multiple business archetypes were developed according to different aspects of EEA's business, such as the source of finance, the beneficiary stakeholders, the information flow and the managing entity. The business archetypes were kept simple in order to highlight all the services that an EE Aggregator is able to provide. These services include attracting customers, ESCOs and investors, pooling projects into a single portfolio, elaborating the EEMs, monitor and verifying the performance of the upgrade, facilitating communication and monetary flows between the stakeholders, editing contractual agreements and managing the business scheme. The development of the BMC and the business model is based on these business archetypes. The main conclusions that we can derive are:

- The participation of the EE Aggregator in a P4P programme can lead to energy upgrades in buildings, including also behavioural measures and rely on metered energy savings. This is essential in order to reduce the carbon footprint of the building sector, increase the wellbeing of end users, and support the reliability and stability of the grid;
- The EE Aggregator is able to attract private funding and integrate it into public based funding by decreasing the risk of investing in an underperforming renovation. Additionally, the EE Aggregator can engage energy suppliers and DSOs as investors by providing value to them through the EEOS or the capacity market, as seen in business archetype. These allow to overcome the relevant investment fragmentation which is typical of the residential sector;
- Project aggregation into a portfolio can relieve building owners from the transaction costs of an EE upgrade. Combined with the EE Aggregator's aforementioned ability to attract third party sources of funding to finance part of the total cost of the EE upgrades, it is more likely for building owners to be persuaded to retrofit their buildings. From this aspect, the EE Aggregator business model facilitates governments to actually reduce the total energy consumption of the building sector;
- The EE business model consists of a long value chain with multiple stakeholders, so the clarity and well-design of its procedures is essential in order to operate and create profit;

- National governments and public authorities could support the EE Aggregator by eliminating possible administrative barriers. They could provide a reliable, safe and clear administrative framework for all the involved stakeholders to operate and interact;
- An operational barrier is the fact that end users' real time energy consumption data is not a publicly available information due to data privacy conservation. The end user should have to contractually agree with energy companies and the EE Aggregator to access and utilise the individual energy consumption data. The EE Aggregator and the programme owner must be able to provide safe communication channels to prevent private data leakage and protect end users.

Finally, this analysis concludes that the EE Aggregator is a promising business entity that can lead the renovation market, accelerate the pace of EE upgrading the building sector and create value or profit for all the engaged stakeholders.

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Appendix A

1. What are the main constraints ESCOs/ DR face to apply their solutions to the residential sector? (multiple choice)

- Low level of energy prices
- Lack of energy intensity to justify investment
- Lack of information and awareness
- High fragmentation of the market
- Legislation and regulation
- High payback periods
- Lack of public subsidies
- Other.

2. What are the main reasons why ESCOs and DR aggregators should focus more on the residential sector? (multiple choice)

- The overall energy saving potential
- The large replication potential
- Access to data sets and analytics
- The current focus of energy policies towards the involvement of the residential sector in decarbonization efforts
- The lack of competition in the residential sector
- Other

3. What kind of initiatives can facilitate ESCOs and aggregators in operating in the residential sector? (multiple choice)

- Innovative financing solutions (like on-bill financing, on-tax financing)
- Standardized programmes grouping large number of residential energy renovation projects enabling for standardized technical and financial solutions
- Energy renovation solutions for condominium buildings
- Other

4. What are the main services that should be provided to achieve an energy efficiency upgrade in the residential field? (multiple choice)

- Retrofitting services
- Smart equipment and automation
- Energy analytics, awareness and guidelines
- Security services and emergency notifications
- Self-consumption management systems
- Energy management strategies
- Innovative financing solutions, making deep retrofits with long pay-back times financeable (on-bill, on-tax financing)

- Other
- 5. What are the main factors to promote so that residential consumers become active participants in the energy market? (multiple choice)**
- New revenue streams from energy market participation
 - Energy bills reduction
 - Increasing energy efficiency and optimization of self-consumption
 - Secure data sharing
 - Increasing comfort and security
 - Innovative financing solutions (on-bill, on-tax financing)
 - Carbon tax shift and tariff schemes
 - Active engagement in energy communities
 - Other
- 6. Deep renovation actions are encouraged by the EC and funding channels, do you think introducing flexibility hinders deep?**
- No, deep renovation is the aim, introducing flexibility is a plus.
 - Perhaps, deep renovation helps to reduce the energy consumption while flexibility aims to use renewable energy sources in an efficient way and does not always reduce energy consumption.
 - Yes, flexibility hinders deep renovation as building owners will opt for flexibility measures that are cheaper than deep renovation.
- 7. When expanding existing energy upgrade offerings or creating new ones: what steps would you focus on? (importance scale)**
- Reach new sectors (e.g., residential) and benefit from a new source of income (very important, moderately important, not important)
 - Integrate multiple services such as flexibility, storage, thermal comfort, etc. (very important, moderately important, not important)
 - Reduce the uncertainty of energy savings (very important, moderately important, not important)
 - Increase economy of scale/ minimise transaction costs (very important, moderately important, not important)
 - Exploit energy efficiency as a resource to address anticipated demand increases (very important, moderately important, not important)
 - Comply with energy efficiency obligations according to EU / national legislation (e.g., Article 7 of the Energy Efficiency Directive) (very important, moderately important, not important)
- 8. What would be the main benefits of aggregation, meaning grouping small end users/projects into larger bundles? (multiple choice)**

- Engagement of hard-to-reach sectors (e.g., residential, SMEs, condominium)
- Reduction/ minimisation of administrative/ transaction costs
- Facilitation of programme implementation
- Minimisation of performance risks for the implementer
- The shift of the energy market power from suppliers to end-users
- Less due diligence work per invested € for investors
- Standardised approach meaning scalable benefits to ESCO's, equipment vendors, investors
- Others

9. What would be the main barriers/ risks when aggregating energy upgrade projects? (multiple choice)

- Increased complexity discouraging other actors and end-users
- Lack of knowledge (e.g., benefits) and acceptance
- Unfavourable cost allocations
- Inefficient administrative procedures
- Current market/policy conditions
- Other

10. Which market stakeholders are currently able to aggregate the savings and the flexibility from large numbers of building renovation projects? (multiple choice)

- ESCOs
- Utilities (included TSO/DSOs)
- Banks
- Local Government
- Technology providers
- Real estate companies
- Other

11. Which market stakeholders are currently interested in investing in energy efficiency projects? (multiple choice)

- Central banks (ECB)
- Retail Banks
- National Governments
- Local Governments
- Pension funds
- Private Financial Institutions
- Insurance companies
- Utilities (including TSO/DSOs)
- Real estate companies
- Citizens
- Other

12. What are, in your opinion, the main barriers for ESCOs to deploy full Pay-for-Performance contracts in the residential sector? (multiple choice)

- Lack of accurate baselining and forecast models
- Complexity of the Performance Measurement and Verification methodologies applicable to the accurate estimation of savings
- Lack of real-time metering and parameter measurement data
- Mistrust of end users on the data capturing and processing systems
- Low perceived economic benefits, no clear economic incentive
- Other

Appendix B

a) Conclusions regarding the market and regulatory framework for each business model.

Market and regulatory framework		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty with market openness and lack of consistency within Europe for flexibility (explicit) • Attractiveness or not, of residential sector for efficiency and flexibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Efficiency as a demand side resource contributing to grid stability (Electricity Market Directive) • Energy Efficiency Obligation schemes (EED Art7) • Pay for Performance valorizes EE services based on advanced MRV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation of flexibility in buildings via implicit and explicit Demand Response • Optimizing the financial and CO₂ savings business case for deep building renovation via the Active building Energy Performance (AEPC model) • AEPC market development in Europe and the role of Active control solutions

b) Conclusions regarding the strategies to promote energy efficiency and reduce costs of the energy transition in the residential sector for each business model.

Strategies to promote energy efficiency and reduce costs of the energy transition in the residential sector		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combining all possible revenue streams in one package. • Data driven solutions to improve ease of implementation. • Engaging prosumers/consumers, user centric. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation into portfolios can unlock private investment in EE. • The current energy crisis shows the real potential of performance-based EE. • P4P allows to quantify and market the extra benefits of EE to system operators and energy utilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the basic EPC business model via AEPC • Electrification of heat supply in combination with PV and intelligent insulation strategy • Active smart heat control, smart EV control

c) Conclusions regarding the technologies and actors for each business model.

Technologies and actors

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short PBP to stimulate financing • Automation/analytics: financially more viable • Maintain comfort levels for residents • Aggregators are more than ESCOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4P to improve EPCs with metered savings and performance guarantees • EE Aggregator: aggregator can be an integration of a technical role and financial role • Advanced Measurement & Verification technologies, can dynamically estimate and market energy efficiency savings and demand side flexibility resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AEPC business model for additional cost & CO2 savings • The role of ESCOs as flexibility aggregators • The integration of active control software for global building flexibility optimization into existing BEMS/EMS systems

d) Conclusions regarding the risks and opportunities for each business model.

Risks and Opportunities		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital infrastructure/ technological developments improve the viability of the solutions. • Large opportunity to reduce energy consumption and provide network services. • Risk in Regulatory /market fragmentation and non standardized, not compatible infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The market is too reassured with deemed savings and the switch to metered savings is not a priority at EU level • Little incentive in the EU so far because grid capacity limits have not been reached yet • The current energy crisis is showing that renewables are not a silver bullet and decarbonizing the evening peak hours will be a real challenge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced M&V to cater for dynamic pricing • Market uptake driven by commercial opportunities (chicken & egg situation) • Role of AEPC project facilitators and project aggregators, besides ESCOs • Push for deep renovation might limit support to AEPC projects.

Appendix C

(1) Which stakeholder group would you count yourself among? If our groups do not match your profile, please let us know your area of activity in the “other” field.

Select one of the following options:

- Building owner/user
- Energy community
- Energy service provider
- Energy utility
- Energy distributor/ transmission system operator
- Public authority
- Policymaker
- Other: _____

(2) What is your country of residence? Help text: The list includes all member states of the European Union. If you come from outside the EU, please use the ‘other’ field.

Select one of the following options:

- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Czechia
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania

- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Other: _____

(3) Have you ever heard of the “Energy Efficiency Aggregator” business model?

Select one of the following options:

- Yes, I am familiar with the concept.
- I have heard of this through this project, but I don't know it very well.
- No, it's the first time I've heard of it.
- Other: _____

(4) Would your organization be interested in cooperating with an Energy Efficiency Aggregator to implement energy efficiency projects?

Select one of the following options:

- Yes
- Yes, it could be interesting
- Not
- Other: _____

(5) What kind of services would you like to get from the Energy Efficiency Aggregator?

Check the options that apply:

- Attracting and engaging customers
- Measuring and aggregating energy savings
- Aggregating energy efficiency projects
- Aggregating funding sources
- Administrating and overviewing the energy efficiency projects
- Communicating and coordinating with all stakeholders involved in the energy efficiency projects
- Elaborating the appropriate energy efficiency measures and guiding end users on changes in consumer behaviour
- Other: _____

Please answer the following questions to rate the importance of different benefits and services expected by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model.

- (6) How important is it to reach new sectors (e.g., residential) and benefit from a new financing opportunity using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

- (7) How important is it to reduce the risk of the investment portfolio by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

- (8) How important is it to reduce the uncertainty of energy savings by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

- (9) How important is it to comply with energy efficiency obligations according to EU / national legislation (e.g., Article 7 of the Energy Efficiency Directive) using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

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(10) How important is it to reduce administrative/ transaction costs by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

(11) How important is it to delegate (part of) the technical risk of financing operations to the Energy Efficiency Aggregator using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

(12) How important is it to exploit energy efficiency as a resource to address anticipated demand increases by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

(13) How important is it to reduce grid expansion costs by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

(14) How important is it to integrate multiple services such as flexibility, storage, thermal comfort, etc. by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

(15) How important is it to reduce energy consumption and increase the well-being of the end-users by using the Energy Efficiency Aggregator business model?

Not important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important

(16) What are the main limitations that could hinder the implementation of the Energy Efficiency Aggregator?

Check the options that apply:

- Lack of knowledge (e.g. benefits, available schemes, etc.)
- Inefficient administrative procedures and/ or legislative framework
- Lack of standardized methods and market participation rules
- Unfavourable cost allocations
- Current market/policy conditions

- Limited technology (e.g., smart meters, automated measurement and verification (M&V) methods, etc.)
- Lack of acceptance (e.g., customers continue to rely on traditional mechanisms)
- Limited recognition of energy efficiency as a grid resource
- Other: _____

Please let us know if we can contact you for future follow-up activities on the SENSEI project.

- a) Would you like to add further aspects to the survey, that we didn't mention? Help text: Please use the text box if you have general comments on the questionnaire. [open field; optional]

_____ (3000 signs possible)

- a) We would like to inform you about our results once we completed analyzing the survey data. If you agree to hearing from us again, please enter your contact email address below.[open field; optional]

Email address: _____(Help text: Your personal data will not be linked to the questionnaire)

Thank you, for contributing to the survey! If you have general questions or comments concerning the survey or our project, feel free to contact us.